

ENER GIZE

SUPPORTING THE CLEAN ENERGY
TRANSITION OF EUROPEAN BUSINESSES

D3.2 User experience maps & user personas

D3.2 – USER EXPERIENCE MAPS & USER PERSONAS

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CER	Comunità Energetiche Rinnovabili (Italian for REC)
EV	Electric Vehicle
GSE	Gestore Servizi Energetici (Italian state-owned energy service system operator)
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
REC	Renewable energy communities
PV	Photovoltaic
UX	User Experience

Executive summary

This deliverable presents the results of extensive user research, which resulted in a set of user personas and user experience maps developed to inform and support the design and implementation of ENERGIZE Acceleration Programme in the four pilot regions of the project: Catalonia (Spain), Valsesia (Italy), Zlín Region (Czech Republic), and Upper Austria (Austria). It is the result of a comprehensive, user-centred research process that aimed to better understand the motivations, barriers, and needs of local stakeholders engaged in energy cooperation.

The work was grounded in a mixed-methods approach, combining desktop research, stakeholder interviews, and surveys conducted with actors across diverse contexts, including public authorities, industrial park managers, energy cooperatives, citizens, and SMEs. The research was complemented by local partners' expertise, allowing for a more contextualised understanding of each region's energy ecosystem.

The synthesis of this data enabled the creation of user personas—fictional, evidence-based archetypes representing key stakeholder groups attitude towards energy cooperation—and user experience maps, which illustrate the typical journey of these users when engaging with ENERGIZE Acceleration Programme. These tools are meant to support ENERGIZE future engagement strategies, training materials development, and the design of resources that are better aligned with users' expectations, concerns, and capacities.

Key insights from the research include:

- **Motivations and priorities** for engaging in energy cooperation, ranging from cost savings and energy independence to environmental concern and local solidarity.
- **Common perceived barriers**, including lack of trust, limited technical knowledge, administrative complexity, and fragmented governance structures.
- **Lessons learned** from existing energy transition and energy cooperation initiatives.
- **Skill gaps** that constrain local actors' ability to participate in or lead energy community efforts, highlighting the need for targeted capacity-building and training formats.

The deliverable closes with possible action points that can mitigate some of the challenges identified and strengthen the credibility and usability of the Acceleration Programme.

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the user personas and user experience maps developed in the context of the ENERGIZE project, a Horizon Europe initiative. ENERGIZE focuses on empowering industry park actors in their energy transition pathways by enhancing their understanding of cooperative energy solutions and showcasing cooperative energy models' viability within selected industrial zones. The work described here is grounded in user research conducted across four pilot regions—Catalonia (Spain), Valsesia (Italy), the Zlín Region (Czech Republic), and Upper Austria (Austria)—which represent diverse regulatory contexts, energy cultures, and levels of maturity in community energy initiatives.

The goal of this deliverable is twofold: first, to generate a deeper understanding of the lived experiences, motivations, and needs of various local stakeholders involved in or affected by energy transition and cooperation efforts in industry parks; and second, to translate these insights into actionable user personas and user journeys that can inform the design, development, and deployment of a capacity building Acceleration Programme.

To achieve this, the project team employed a user-centred design approach, grounded in participatory methods and mixed data collection techniques—including desktop research, interviews, surveys, and close collaboration with local partners. The resulting insights were analysed using both qualitative thematic and quantitative data analysis, ensuring a robust and nuanced understanding of stakeholder behaviours and perceptions.

By better understanding the needs, barriers and business objectives of users in industrial parks, the project aims to pave the way to the creation of sustainable energy communities. Therefore, this task mapped and defined specific roles of local stakeholders within the planned co-creation process. Moreover, the user research also aimed to identify critical needs, skills gaps and commonly overlooked challenges that local stakeholders face.

1.1 What are user personas and user experience maps?

To make our findings accessible and actionable, we synthesised the results into two key formats commonly used in design and innovation work:

- **User personas** are fictional but evidence-based profiles that represent key stakeholder types identified in each region. They are not meant to be perfect representations of any one individual but rather to illustrate the goals, challenges, behaviours, and attitudes of groups of users with similar characteristics or experiences. In the context of ENERGIZE, personas help to better understand the diversity of users who could be involved in or impacted by the project capacity building programme and energy cooperation initiatives—such as municipal officers, business owners, or energy professionals.
- **User experience (UX) maps** are visual tools that trace the typical journey a persona might go through when engaging with the project Acceleration Programme—from initial awareness, through decision-making, to active participation or withdrawal. These maps help identify pain points, motivators, and opportunities for intervention, providing practical guidance for improving user engagement, service delivery, and customer support.

By developing personas and UX maps tailored to each pilot region, this deliverable bridges the gap between abstract system design and the day-to-day realities of end users. On a broader level, these tools are especially useful for project partners, local authorities, and other energy transition actors who wish to ensure that their strategies are responsive to real-world needs and capacities.

Importantly, the personas and experience maps presented here are not static deliverables. They are intended to support iterative design and implementation processes throughout the project, especially in the co-design of training formats and engagement activities.

Through this bottom-up approach, this deliverable contributes to the broader aim of ENERGIZE: to foster just, inclusive, and locally embedded energy transitions and cooperations, driven not only by technological innovation but also by social and organisational transformation.

2 Methodology

2.1 1. Approach and Scope

The methodology for developing user experience maps and user personas in the ENERGIZE project is designed to provide a comprehensive understanding of stakeholder roles, needs, and challenges in the energy transition, to provide an evidence-based ground for the co-creation of regional urban-industrial energy cooperations. This process is grounded in participatory research methods, ensuring that insights are drawn from real-world stakeholder experiences. The methodological approach is structured around four core objectives:

1. **Mapping stakeholders in the pilots** – Creating a taxonomy of actors to be involved in the co-creation process.
2. **Detecting priorities and needs** – Understanding stakeholders' motivations, expectations, and decision-making processes concerning energy.
3. **Identifying and addressing barriers** – Mapping economic, technical, policy, and perceptual obstacles that hinder energy cooperation.
4. **Analysing skills gaps in training** – Identifying knowledge deficiencies and training needs to support energy cooperation formation.
5. **Developing personas and their journeys** – Map challenges, barriers and opportunities for the ENERGIZE Acceleration Programme by following the journey of exemplary stakeholders.

To achieve these objectives, a mixed-methods approach was employed, combining desktop research, stakeholder interviews, and surveys. This triangulation of data sources ensures a robust and nuanced understanding of user experiences across the four industrial park pilots.

2.2 Data Collection Methods and Analysis

2.2.1 Desktop Research and local partners consultation

The first phase of the study involved extensive secondary research to establish a foundational understanding of the energy landscape, policy frameworks, and existing training resources relevant to energy communities. This included:

- Reviewing academic and grey literature on energy communities and stakeholder engagement.
- Analysing policy documents, reports, and guidelines at the EU and national levels.
- Examining previous projects and case studies on industrial park energy transitions.
- Leverage WP2 deliverables content for contextualisation.

During the Kick-off, partners were involved in a workshop to map local stakeholders. The exercise was further refined during the General Assembly in February 2025 to detect key messages for each stakeholder type. In the same occasion, one draft user experience map was created for each pilot.

2.2.2 Stakeholder Interviews

24 in-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted with identified key stakeholders across the four pilots: Catalonia, Valsesia, Zlín and Upper Austria. The interviews were conducted with the support of local pilot leaders from ICAEN, ENGREEN, EAZK, EI-JKU. This allowed the conducting of interviews in the local languages, i.e. Catalan, Italian, Czech and German and the opportunity for pilots to build further relationships with key stakeholders. The interviews lasted around 60-minutes and were recorded (with consent) to be transcribed for later thematic analysis.

The selection of interviewees was based on their involvement in energy-related decision-making and represented:

- Industrial park managers
- Energy community managers, consultants and technicians
- Business representatives (SMEs and large enterprises)
- Local policymakers
- Community representatives

The interview followed a guide with 10 questions¹ and covered topics such as: current energy policies and goals in the organisation; understanding and perception of energy cooperation; barriers to participation and collaboration in the realm of energy; most demanded training topics and favourite learning supports/media. Representatives of energy communities were asked also to highlight their learnings and success factors.

Qualitative data from interviews were thematically analysed to identify recurring patterns in stakeholder experiences, needs, and challenges. Themes were grouped into categories such as:

- Motivation for energy cooperation
- Perceived barriers and challenges for cooperation
- Lessons learned from existing energy communities
- Knowledge gaps
- Preferred training formats

These insights were valuable in understanding the broader context of the pilots and the local business in the area. The analysis showed the diversity of local challenges and opportunities, as well as, indicating the readiness of the pilots and potential barriers in creating energy communities within the industrial parks. This information was essential in the development of the user personas and experience maps. They will also inform tasks 3.3 and 5.2.

2.2.3 Surveys

A total of 185 answers, of which 115 were complete, were received through surveys. Two surveys were developed: one for the Catalan pilot which can already refer to an existing energy community and a second one for the remaining three pilots. The survey in Catalan differs from the other languages because it includes some questions regarding lessons learnt from managing/being part of an energy community, to collect more inputs from Manresa Il·lumina Energy Community.² Using two surveys allowed to ask more specific questions tailored to the local conditions of the pilots. Moreover, the surveys were translated into the four local languages using the online survey software SurveyMonkey. The surveys were distributed through local partners' channels (mainly mailing) to a broader group of stakeholders to complement the qualitative insights from interviews.

The themes the surveys investigated were:

- Awareness and interest in energy communities.
- Current renewables installations and energy-related plans for the near future.
- Self-assessment of skills and knowledge gaps.
- Perceived benefits and barriers to engagement.
- Preferred formats for training and capacity-building initiatives.

¹ See Annex 1 for the full set of questions.

² Link to survey in Catalan: <https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/KWXKDX7>
Link to survey in Italian, Czech and Austrian: <https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/RZRYGK8>

Survey data was analysed using descriptive statistics to quantify stakeholder awareness levels, training needs, and perceptions of energy cooperation. For the Catalan pilot results were compared across Manresa and different industrial parks to contextualise the project lighthouse energy community. While the response rate of the Catalan case was high 128 (73 fully completed) responses, whereas despite several outreach waves (in-person, via telephone and email), in other pilots the numbers were much lower (Zlín Region: 38 (30 completed), Valsesia: 13 (completed 8), Upper Austria: 6 (4 completed)). These limitations highlight the need for further outreach and community work through the project and will be further addressed in the pilot specific section in section 3.

2.3 Persona and user experience maps development

The collected data was analysed using a combination of qualitative and quantitative analyses to generate detailed user personas and experience maps. The personas and maps assist in designing targeted, practical solutions that align with users' actual behaviours and challenges, rather than relying on assumptions. Both the user personas and user experience maps will be essential in the further development of tasks 3.3 and 5.2.

2.3.1 User personas development

The personas were developed based on qualitative and quantitative insights. Reoccurring behaviours, views and attitudes were distilled into detailed user personas to represent key stakeholder groups in the four pilots. The personas also reflect differing knowledge, interest and readiness for energy communities, that emerged from the data and differed across the pilots.

To ensure an actionable usage of the personas, two contrasting personas per pilot were developed, and each reflects:

- Background information (role, sector...)
- Key motivations and priorities for energy cooperation
- Pain points and barriers concerning energy cooperation
- Specific training and capacity-building needs
- Opportunities for engagement along their interaction arc with the project

These personas serve as actionable tools for designing tailored training interventions and engagement strategies within the ENERGIZE project.

2.3.2 User experience maps Development

The user maps visualise all the steps users, represented by one of the developed personas, are going through when interacting with the ENERGIZE acceleration programme and general interaction with the project.

The steps include:

1. Awareness – users realise they have problems/barriers concerning the energy transition and energy cooperation
2. Consideration – users access whether ENERGIZE and its activities can offer help in solving their issue
3. Sign up – users enroll to the platform and training program
4. Use – users carry out the training online and face to face
5. Advocacy – users become advocates for ENERGIZE and the training programme

Figure 1 Layout user experience maps

For each step that the user takes, goals, actions, touchpoints, pain points and opportunities are also laid out, based on each persona’s background, key motivations and barriers they face. Pilot leaders also evaluated the user experience maps and personas during the project’s General Assembly in February 2025 and their feedback was integrated in the finalised version in section 3. The user maps are actionable tools that will be used to create the enrolment process, key selling points and content for the acceleration platform, as well as to design workshops and other face-to-face interactions with stakeholders in the pilots.

3 Pilot profiles

3.1 Region of Catalonia (Spain)

Situated in the northeastern Iberian Peninsula, Catalonia is Spain's sixth largest autonomous community by area and the second most populous, with around 8 million inhabitants. It is one of the country's most economically dynamic regions, contributing approximately 20% of Spain's GDP.

Catalonia has a highly diversified economy, historically rooted in textiles, shipbuilding, and agriculture but now driven by automotive manufacturing, chemicals, pharmaceuticals, ICT, finance, and tourism. The Barcelona metropolitan area is a key economic hub, home to multinational corporations, start-ups, and research institutions. Catalonia also maintains a strong agri-food sector, with products such as wine, olive oil, and cured meats gaining international recognition. However, industrial shifts and economic crises—most notably the 2008 financial crash and the 2020 pandemic downturn—have led to structural adjustments in key sectors, including a transition towards digitalisation, innovation and sustainability-focused industries.

In 2023, despite a challenging global context marked by geopolitical tensions and inflationary pressures, Catalonia's economy grew by 2.6%, outperforming the European Union average. The industrial sector remains a key pillar of the Catalan economy, contributing 18.6% of the region's GDP and employing 13.9% of the workforce ("Informe anual sobre la indústria a Catalunya," n.d.). Catalonia is a leading industrial region in Spain, accounting for over 22% of the country's industrial GDP and nearly 30% of national exports. The sector is highly export-oriented (34.6% of sales go abroad) and shows strong investment in innovation and R&D.

Key industries include food, automotive, pharmaceuticals, electronics, textiles, and leather. The food sector is the largest in terms of jobs, while tech-intensive sectors like pharmaceuticals and electronics have surpassed pre-pandemic levels. Traditional sectors like textiles and apparel are in decline, while leather and footwear showed signs of recovery.

Catalonia's industry remains a key economic driver, with strong international presence and growing innovation capacity.

3.1.1 Energy context and regulation

Catalonia is a key player in Spain's renewable energy transition. In 2024, with a total of **37,508.4 GWh**, it was the autonomous community with the highest electricity production **amounting to a 14.3% of the national generation (according to ESIOS, Red Eléctrica data hubs)**. It ranked second in terms of emission-free electricity generation, reaching 29332 GWh. Furthermore, renewable generation in 2024 constituted 19.1% of the overall energy mix in Catalonia. The region has significant wind and solar energy potential, and energy community projects are gaining traction, particularly in rural and peri-urban areas. The Catalan Energy Institute (ICAEN) plays a key role in promoting self-consumption, energy efficiency, and decentralised production models. In 2023 ICAEN developed the Energy Outlook of Catalonia (PROENCAT 2050), which outlines the long-term vision for the region's energy system. The present Government-approved outlook sets out a 2050 scenario aimed at achieving net-zero greenhouse gas emissions across the energy system. This is achieved through a 57% in final energy intensity between 2017 and 2050 (**final energy use per unit of GDP**), the deployment of a 100% renewable electricity system, extensive electrification of demand, and the shift from fossil to renewable fuels.

In Catalonia, energy communities are increasingly seen as a key instrument to accelerate the energy transition and promote citizen and stakeholder engagement. Local initiatives are emerging across diverse contexts—including municipalities, residential areas, and industrial parks—exploring models of shared self-consumption and renewable energy deployment. In the industrial sector, this deployment is still recent, but promising examples are already emerging, such as the energy communities in the Bufalvent industrial park in Manresa. These cases demonstrate the viability of collective energy projects in industrial

environments. Beyond shared generation, these communities open the door to broader initiatives, such as the joint management of electric mobility services or district heating networks.

To facilitate this growing movement, the Catalan Institute for Energy (ICAEN) and the Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC) are developing the platform comunitatenergetica.cat. The platform serves as a space for awareness-raising, knowledge sharing, and visibility of energy communities in Catalonia, aiming to support both emerging and consolidated initiatives. Fostering collaboration and access to resources contributes to the broader goal of a fair, distributed, and participatory energy system aligned with regional and EU energy policies.

3.1.2 The Manresa energy community

A successful initiative in Catalonia's energy transition in industry parks is the Manresa Il·lumina energy community, the first industrial one in Spain. Located in the Bages region, this pioneering project focuses on collective self-consumption and local renewable energy generation. The initiative, powered by the Industrial Association of Bufalvent industrial district, brings together 36 local businesses to develop a shared solar energy infrastructure, reducing dependency on traditional power suppliers and lowering electricity costs. In addition to generating clean energy, the project aims to lower energy consumption and reduce the environmental impact of mobility within the industrial park. To achieve this, plans include electrifying the workforce vehicle fleet with electric chargers powered by energy from solar and wind installations. The project also includes the development of thermal energy solutions through a biomass heat network, renewable energy sourced from nearby Bages forests, and the collective purchase of renewable electricity to meet the demand not covered by solar installations.

The community has begun the installation of solar panels with a total power of 1,033 kWp, covering 10 company roofs in a first phase of the project. In 2024, it has been awarded the prize for the best energy community in Spain at the first edition of the Green CommYOUunity Awards, held in Madrid (*NOTICIA*, n.d.). The project aligns with Catalonia's broader vision of energy sovereignty and climate neutrality, inspiring similar efforts in other municipalities.

Manresa Il·lumina is an advanced case for ENERGIZE, and it will contribute with lessons learnt to the creation of the Acceleration Programme. In the rest of Catalonia, ENERGIZE aims to support the shift to Industrial Renewable Energy Communities, particularly in energy-intensive sectors such as manufacturing.

3.1.3 Stakeholder mapping

The actors identified in Catalonia for co-creation can be grouped into the following categories:

- Industrial parks and associations
- Financial entities and investors
- Energy businesses (operators, distributors, utilities, consultancies, installers, ESCOs)
- Public administration and energy agencies
- Energy communities
- Individual industries in industrial parks

Stakeholder	Type	Relevance
Molanes	Industrial parks and associations	Catalonia counts 1500+ Industrial parks. 1,440 Industrial Parks in Southern Catalonia + 120 Industrial Parks in Northern Catalonia.
Salt		
Cornella de Terri		
Cornella de Llobregat		
Castelvi de Rosanes		

Business Association of Industrial Parks		They will be involved to answer the survey and as beneficiaries of the Acceleration Programme.
PIMEC		
UPIC		
Business Association Bufalvent		
Business Association Castelgall		
Business Association Els Dolors		
Business Association Els Trullols		
Business Association Sant Vicent de Castelets		
Fiare	Financial entities and investors	They will be involved to provide inputs on the financial topics of the Acceleration Programme.
Ecrowd		
Suma Capital		
Triodos Banc		
ICF		
Coop 57		
SOM COMUNITATS	Energy businesses	They will be involved as ambassadors of the Acceleration Programme, and be proposed to include it in their offering.
KMO ENERGY		
CEFIMER		
PROISOTECH		
EMELCAT		
CIVIT ENERGX		
OSONA ENERGIA		
ICAEN	Public administration and energy agencies	They will be involved as ambassadors and partners of the Acceleration Programme, that can support the reach of the energy targets.
Energy Transition Offices		
AMB		
Diputacions		
Manresa Il·lumina	Energy communities	They will be involved to answer the survey and as beneficiaries of the Acceleration Programme.
Vic		
Agroreus		
Pla de l'Estany		
Les Planes		
N/A	Individual industries	They will be involved to answer the survey and as beneficiaries of the Acceleration Programme.

Table 1 Stakeholder mapping Catalonia

Stakeholders Map Catalunya

Figure 2 - Stakeholder map in Catalonia

3.1.4 Interviewees' profile

The following stakeholders were interviewed in the Manresa area:

- Manresa Il·lumina community manager & industry association manager
- Bufalvent Industry Association president
- Consultant who supported the structuring of Manresa Il·lumina community
- Representative of Manresa municipality
- Three representatives of industrial companies part of Manresa Il·lumina community
- CEO of a company specialised in PV installations

3.1.5 Survey respondents' profile

The Catalan pilot counts 128 responses to the survey; the complete ones are 53 coming from the Manresa pilot area plus another 20 identified as based in other industrial areas. To ensure broad participation, ICAEN implemented a multi-channel dissemination strategy for the survey. This included direct mailing to approximately 50 key stakeholders, targeted mailing to the industrial sector which reached around 200 professionals, and publication through ICAEN's official newsletter, thereby maximizing visibility among its network of contacts and collaborators.

In Manresa and the Bufalvent industrial area, 34% of respondents represent small companies with fewer than 30 employees, while 19% are micro-enterprises with fewer than 5 employees. Only 13% are larger firms with more than 30 employees. The most represented sectors include metal production and distribution, automotive, services, transport, and textiles. Consulting and service companies account for

17% of the sample. The majority of respondents hold decision-making roles: 45% are CEOs, and 30% are senior managers or heads of departments.

The most common energy installation among these companies is heat pumps (50%), followed by photovoltaic (PV) systems (43%), district heating and cooling systems (28%), and electric vehicle (EV) charging stations (24%). A significant **75% of installations were self-financed**, while 35% benefitted from public incentives. Industrial machinery and HVAC systems were identified as the main energy-consuming assets.

In contrast, **companies based in other industrial areas** present a different profile. Here, **45% are large enterprises with more than 30 employees**, and 20% are small businesses. These companies span a wide variety of sectors, including metallurgy, food processing (including animal feed), textiles, chemicals and plastics, ceramics and bricks, and automotive.

Their respondent roles are similarly senior: 45% are senior managers or department heads, followed by CEOs and managing directors. Other roles include technical staff, deputy directors, and directors of business associations.

In terms of energy infrastructure, **65% of these companies have installed solar panels, 45% have EV charging stations, and 35% use heat pumps.** District heating systems are present in 25% of cases, while 20% reported having no energy installations at all.

To finance their energy installations, 64% of respondents indicated a combination of public incentives and own funds, while a smaller share (23%) reported relying on loans. When asked about the most energy-intensive assets, 89% identified industrial machinery, followed by HVAC systems at 79%.

In the final open-ended section of the survey, where participants were invited to share any additional thoughts or issues not previously covered, several noteworthy inputs emerged:

- “The tedious bureaucratic process involved in any renewable installation is not discussed, despite the publicity or propaganda surrounding the measures announced by the administration.”
- “Renovation of roofs with asbestos”
- “The delay in the payment of subsidies”
- “Conflict resolution issues with the administration and distributors”

These comments highlight ongoing administrative and technical challenges actors in the Manresa area face.

3.1.6 Priorities and motivations for the energy transition

3.1.6.1 *Results from interviews to Manresa stakeholders*

Many companies in Manresa had already sustainability initiatives before the establishment of the energy community, such as PV installations, ISO certifications and regular renewal of their equipment. **The reasons to join forces in an energy cooperation are diverse, covering the personal sphere and values, economic considerations and corporate strategy.** As the CEO of a local industry stated:

“Basically, it was for environmental reasons. I have solar panels at home out of personal conviction; for me, it’s an important motivation. At the company level, there’s also long-term economic savings, once you’ve amortized the initial capital investment and the loans are being repaid. Regarding financing, it also implies economic savings, energy savings, and decreases dependence on these large companies that, well, at least here in our country... honestly, there’s not much desire to depend on them.”

Overall, **their main self-reported priorities can be resumed in reducing energy consumption and cost savings.** For an energy installer instead, “their primary motivation is economic”. Indeed, the potential to

add value to surplus energy makes ECs an attractive option, matched with the reassurance that nearby production and consumption is more secure in face of unexpected rises in the prices. Business development opportunities further incentivise participation, particularly for companies working with clients who share similar sustainability goals.

3.1.6.2 *Results from survey in the Manresa area*

Over the next five years, **39% of Manresa respondents plan to install solar panels, while 35% have no plans** for any such installation. In addition, 26% intend to set up electric vehicle (EV) charging stations. When it comes to energy goals for this period, there is broad agreement that **reducing costs** is the primary objective, **followed by increasing environmental sustainability** (65%). Other goals include joining an energy community (26%), adopting renewable energy sources (23%), and achieving energy autonomy (21%).

Currently, 64% of respondents are not part of the local energy community, but **61% of these non-members are interested in joining**. The main motivation for joining is **cost savings**, followed by **reducing carbon footprint** (62%), **long-term sustainability** (53%), energy security (50%), improved reputation, and risk mitigation (38%). Additionally, 31% are attracted by the potential for innovation, while 28% see regulatory incentives as an advantage. A further 18% highlighted the importance of knowledge sharing, collaboration, and influencing collective local decision-making.

3.1.6.3 *Results from survey in other Catalan industry parks*

Among stakeholders outside Manresa, the most common installations planned for the next five years are **solar panels** (55%), followed by **EV charging stations** (30%) and batteries (20%). The primary energy goals are **reducing costs** (85%), **increasing environmental sustainability** (65%), **achieving energy autonomy** (40%), and adopting renewables (35%).

Currently, **just 10% are members of an energy community**. However, 75% of those who are not members are interested in joining one. The key motivations for joining are **cost savings** (82%), **long-term sustainability goals** (76%), **energy security and improved sustainability** (52%), supporting local economic growth, and mitigating risks (41%).

3.1.6.4 *Discussion*

Cost reduction and environmental sustainability stand out as the primary energy goals for the near future. There is a notable interest in joining an energy community, with cost savings being the leading motivation. Interestingly, in Manresa, social factors—such as knowledge sharing and community building—play a more significant role compared to other districts. This may be influenced by the strong presence of the local business association.

Looking ahead, the most commonly planned installations are solar panels and EV charging stations, reflecting a broader push toward energy autonomy and greater reliance on renewables.

Figure 3: Energy goals for the coming 5 years (Catalonia)

Figure 4: Motivations for joining an EC (Catalonia)

3.1.7 Barriers for energy cooperation

3.1.7.1 Results from interviews with Manresa stakeholders

During interviews, both energy professionals and industry representatives lamented that many companies have **asbestos cement on their roofs**, which must be removed (with consequent delays and extra investments)³ before installing photovoltaic systems. Rented warehouses with asbestos cement are also an issue, as tenants don't want to bother the owner or make the investment since it's not their property. This significant material barrier has led to a decreasing interest in solar panels. Indeed, **the demand for PV has significantly slowed compared to its peak in 2022, which coincided with a growth in energy prices**. In 2023, suppliers began to have a surplus of materials, and the end of Next Generation subsidies and lower energy prices led to a decrease in demand for PV. **In 2024, demand dropped by 70% and energy prices by 50% compared to 2022**. According to one installer, there is now an excess of materials on the market, which has disappointed people and slowed the momentum.

³ The Catalan Waste Agency (Agència de Residus de Catalunya) offers financial assistance to support the safe removal of asbestos-containing materials from buildings and structures throughout Catalonia. Nonetheless, this assistance was not cited by interviewees.

Communicating clearly the mission of the energy community and keeping an open discussion among community members has been identified as an entry barrier for cooperation. The process is in constant evolution, and it was not granted at the beginning to have clarity on the vision, guidance for members (or wannabe ones) and detailed planning. All community members, although extremely positive about their membership, highlighted that **it is hard to notice benefits in the short term**: joining the community is an investment in the future, and one must not underestimate the length of the set-up process.

The uncertainty of controlling energy monopolies, especially distributors, is another barrier, since they tend to cause delays with connection permits and other procedures. *“Legally, they’re supposed to promote it, but electric distributors have no interest in deploying energy communities, and it’s well-known in the sector that they put up every possible barrier. Ultimately, we’re connecting our solar panels to their grid, and in doing so, we’re adding renewable energy to their system. This creates problems for them, as their grid becomes overloaded. Although we pay for it, it causes issues for them”.*

In general, interviewees report that **Spain does not have a stable legal framework** that guarantees the community's profitability and attractiveness for the partners. The 100kw limit for collective installations results in a long payback period. The 2 km radius is also a limiting factor. Additionally, while public subsidies are available, such as those provided by ICAEN under the IDAE programmes, each project is unique and requires a detailed, manual evaluation. This **process can be time-consuming** because of the complexity and diversity of the projects being submitted. The need for individualised assessment ensures that each proposal is thoroughly reviewed, but also contributes to longer timelines. Each project has its unique characteristics, and in the private sector, new ideas and concerns are emerging, particularly around solutions for energy storage and surplus energy from weekends. Bureaucracy associated with low energy literacy is also a complicated issue: people don't know much about energy cooperatives, and there is even ignorance within the administration.

This uncertainty reflects in **a lack of trust: people have become sceptical about government funds**, such as Next Generation funds, reaching them. Even when a grant application seems well-received, the company may not receive the funds because of missing invoices, improper documentation, etc. This situation also reveals a broader societal tension: while there is strong demand for rapid results and public funding, this is often accompanied by limited awareness of the administrative procedures and complexities involved in ensuring fair and transparent distribution. There is a prevailing expectation for immediate action which, when met with inevitable delays or procedural challenges, can easily lead to criticism of public authorities.

3.1.7.2 Results from survey in the Manresa area

The most significant barrier to joining the energy community in Manresa is the **complexity of administrative procedures (58%), followed by high upfront costs (50%) and concerns over the uncertainty and time frame of return on investment (47%)**. Additionally, 29% of respondents cite regulatory hurdles and the slower decision-making process when working collectively rather than independently. Internal resource constraints, including a lack of time and staff to actively engage with the community, pose a challenge for 23% of respondents. Lastly, 20% express concerns about reduced flexibility and autonomy in decision-making within the community structure.

3.1.7.3 Results from survey in other Catalan industry parks

The primary barrier to joining an energy community is the **high upfront cost**, cited by 82% of participants. The complexity of administrative and operational procedures when collaborating with other members is also a major concern. Furthermore, **65% highlight uncertainties around the return on investment** and the time required to see financial benefits. A lack of incentives and financial schemes, along with regulatory hurdles and unclear guidance, is reported by 52% of respondents. Additionally, 41% feel that energy communities receive insufficient recognition in the region. Notably, 35% express concerns about the lengthy process involved in developing energy projects collectively compared to working independently.

3.1.7.4 Discussion

The perceived difficulties in joining an Energy Community (EC) vary between Manresa Il·lumina and other areas. In our main pilot focus, Manresa, the most significant concern is the **complexity of administrative procedures**, followed closely by other barriers. In contrast, in regions without a well-established lighthouse community, **high upfront costs** emerge as the primary obstacle.

Across all areas, **uncertainty**—whether related to return on investment, project timeframes, or regulatory procedures—plays a major role in discouraging participation.

Additionally, survey open comments and interviews reveal a broader **lack of trust** in government support and the willingness of energy distributors to collaborate. Another critical infrastructural challenge is the widespread presence of **asbestos** in industrial hangars and facilities, which significantly hinders the installation of solar panels.

Figure 5: barriers to energy cooperation, survey highlights (Catalonia)

3.1.8 Lessons learned from Manresa

3.1.8.1 Results from interviews with Manresa stakeholders

Stakeholders described **collaboration as challenging for the Catalan business culture**. Companies tend to be quite individualistic, and it's difficult for them to work as a group. They usually come together only when there's a genuine need. This is exactly what happened three years ago when energy prices soared. This led to the creation of the Manresa Il·lumina energy community structure. The community establishment was successful because it could rely on two key assets: strong leadership and the pre-existing industry association.

All interviewees agreed that **having a person who coordinates and fosters unity among companies has been key**. In the Bufalvent industry park, the community manager is considered unanimously a leader. *"She already has the trust of the business owners because she's been working there for 30 years. If*

Montse—who you know as a strong person—says, “Tomorrow we’re doing this,” the other business owners say, “Okay.” On the other hand, **the community manager stressed the importance of trust**: “From my perspective, the key success factor is this: trust. We know each other and have already worked together in other areas, such as safety, work-life balance, signage, and mobility.” **The presence of the Bufalvent industry association**, which by a matter of fact was already behaving as a community and gathers 95% of the companies in the area, worked as a catalyst and leveraged pre-existing individual efforts of companies in going sustainable. Having a well-organised community also works as an engine to make it attractive to further companies, and the municipality has become much faster over the years in delivering permits.

The main challenges faced by the management staff concerned understanding the complexity of the technical and legal aspects, which slowed down the set-up process and the actual exchange of energy within the community. An interviewee pointed out that a middle ground between ambition and feasibility was crucial for future improvements and other communities. They propose that the community could start by targeting people who already have private solar panels and ask them to sell electricity to their neighbours instead of commercial operators, with the advantage that they don't have to pay transportation fees. “This has not been considered and it’s a shame, as the community could already be functioning.”

Finally, one of the key management staff underlined that **companies need concreteness to be convinced to join a community**: “One of the main lessons is that you have to speak their language, and that language is called a business plan.” - he explained, referring to the initial failed attempts to onboard members.

3.1.8.2 Results from survey in the Manresa area

The primary benefit reported by community members is **reduced energy costs**, followed by increased **energy efficiency** (66%). Other significant advantages include **access to subsidies and incentives** (55%), **new collaborative opportunities** (50%), and **knowledge sharing** with other members, which ranks equally with **community empowerment** (33%). Additionally, 22% highlight improved **access to innovative energy solutions, simplified regulatory compliance**, and enhanced **green branding**.

Self-reported learnings from participants reflect both practical and strategic insights. Among the most common reflections are:

- “Positive impact and quick amortisation for the company”
- “Purchase of generated energy at a reasonable price”
- “Understanding how the energy market works and finding better prices”
- “Having a certain level of energy independence is positive”
- “Operation of renewables, financing information”
- “Collaboration among enterprises”
- “Technical and economic knowledge of how renewables work”
- “The innovation of the project is key to the energy transition in industrial parks.”
- “Nothing yet, we are at the beginning”.

3.1.8.3 Results from survey in other Catalan industry parks

Respondents part of an energy community **agree unanimously that reduced energy costs are the main benefit** of their membership. **Resilience to market fluctuations** and more **sustainable operations** are remarked by the 60%, followed by 40% indicating also as benefits **energy efficiency, access to renewable energy, faster adoption** of renewables, **community empowerment**, and **green branding**.

Only half of them shared their lessons learned, which resumes to “nothing” for almost all. The few responses are:

- “Enormous and discouraging bureaucratic difficulty in anything related to the installation of solar panels, despite the publicity or propaganda of the measures announced by the administration”
- “That it is important”

- “Better knowledge of the market”
- “We struggle to raise awareness among companies to encourage their participation in the energy community.”

3.1.8.4 Discussion

A key success factor of the Manresa Il-lumina community is its strong **leadership**, both through its dedicated manager and the Bufalvent industry association. Their role in fostering **trust** and creating a solid foundation has been crucial in driving engagement. Challenges and setbacks are inevitable, but they can be navigated by striking a balance between feasibility and ambition while providing entrepreneurs with clear financial projections and **concrete planning**. Although cost reduction is cited as the main expected benefit, this remains largely a future projection rather than a current reality, as most interviewees indicate that they have **yet to experience tangible financial gains**.

3.1.9 Skill gaps and training formats

3.1.9.1 Results from interviews with Manresa stakeholders

Interviewees stressed that entrepreneurs need technical support for energy issues because it is an aspect that is not present in the current training. **Technical support should be a requirement to set up this type of project, and this is very difficult to finance**. They pointed out that there should be a state program to support these types of initiatives: if the energy transition in industrial parks is truly a political priority, then it is necessary to invest and provide technical and economic resources to advance in this direction.

While it was noted that there are many experts in installing photovoltaic panels and analysing consumption, skills around solving the legal challenges of organising an energy community are scarce. Therefore, **legal advice becomes the key and most important piece for advancing these projects**. In the case of Manresa Il-lumina, navigating financing and subsidies has been learned along the way, also because each grant is different and values different criteria.

The most demanded training topics concern the set-up and functioning of energy communities, from business modelling to governance to communication with members. Interviewees converged in identifying the **managers of the Manresa community as target beneficiaries of the trainings**. **Funding schemes also raised high interest**, especially any guidance that can support the understanding of the financing of the project, return on investment, the payback time frame and at what price does the entrepreneur acquire energy *“because, in the end, the most important thing for the entrepreneur is that this is profitable and feasible”*.

Interviewees also showed interest in **knowing more about European objectives**, to build coherence and knowing that the cooperation is viable to apply for future subsidies and aids. Among renewable energy sources, the ones which raised more consensus for training **are solar, wind, aérothermal and biomass**, the latter because the area is surrounded by forests. **Waste management** was also highlighted. Less interest was voiced for district heating and managing the end life of solar panels.

In terms of formats, interviewees would prefer **online trainings** (especially live webinars), and **online thematic workshops** combined with **individual coaching** and **face-to-face site visits**.

3.1.9.2 Results from survey in the Manresa area

A majority of respondents (47%) have a basic understanding of key energy concepts, while 23% report having good knowledge, and 22% know little about the topic. Only 37% participated in energy-related events or training sessions in 2024, with most of these focusing on energy communities.

Regarding renewable energy production technologies, the most in-demand training topic is **renewable energy basics** (55%), followed by **batteries** (40%), **solar energy** (37%), **geothermal energy** (27%), and **wind energy** (22%).

For energy communities, the most popular training topic is **how energy is produced and distributed within a community** (50%), followed by **a general introduction to energy communities and success stories from existing ones** (46%). Other areas of interest include **technical installations and related software** (40%), **business models** (36%), and **organisational models** (27%).

In terms of financing, **EU funds** are the most sought-after topic (65%), followed by **regional funding opportunities** (52%).

Regarding policies and regulations, respondents are most interested in **national regulations on renewable energy and energy efficiency**. When it comes to training formats, 45% would feel comfortable attending **online webinars**, followed by **self-paced online training modules** (32%) and **in-person thematic workshops** (20%).

3.1.9.3 *Results from survey in other industry parks*

Only 10% of respondents consider themselves experts in energy, while the majority report having **good knowledge** or at least an understanding of the **main concepts**. **60% did not attend** any energy-related event or training in 2024. Among those who did, **energy communities** emerged as the most common topic.

When asked about their preferred local renewable energy production training, **solar energy** was the most requested (58%), followed by **energy storage** and **renewable energy basics**.

For **energy communities**, the most popular topic is **success stories from other regions** (73%), followed by **energy production and sharing dynamics** (66%), along with **governance, organisational models, and business models**.

Regarding **financing**, the most in-demand topics are **EU funding programmes and structural investments**. On **policies and regulations**, respondents are most interested in **national energy efficiency regulations**, followed by **national and European regulations on energy communities**.

In terms of **training formats**, **live webinars** are the most preferred (59%), followed by **individual coaching** (40%).

3.1.9.4 *Discussion*

Catalan stakeholders admittedly **lack knowledge** around energy, especially but not only about legal and technical aspects. There is high interest for learning more about the **set-up, management, governance of energy communities**, and for learning from the experience of established ones. **Solar energy, renewables basics and batteries** are the most interesting technical aspects. There is interest for going more in-depth in **EU and regional funds and policies** concerning the energy transition.

Overall, **live webinars and self-paced online modules** are the training format that got more demand, followed by **individual coaching** and thematic **workshops in presence**.

3.1.10 User personas and user experience maps

Based on the data collected, two main user profiles emerged as key targets for the project. The first is a "**Proficient**" persona—individuals who are already actively engaged in energy communities, either as leaders or members. They possess a solid understanding of energy concepts, are familiar with the dynamics of collective energy production and sharing, and often seek more advanced knowledge on governance models, funding mechanisms, and technical solutions.

The second is the **"Wannabe"** persona—individuals who express interest or curiosity in energy cooperation but have not yet taken part in any related initiatives. Their knowledge of energy topics is more basic, and they are particularly drawn to accessible introductions, inspiring success stories, and practical guidance on how to get involved.

This distinction reflects the varying levels of awareness, motivation, and experience within the project’s target audience. It also aligns with insights from Catalonia, the project’s most advanced region in terms of energy cooperation. Recognising these two personas enables us to better tailor outreach, capacity-building, and support strategies, and ensures that the user experience maps capture the specific needs, expectations, and potential barriers faced by each group.

The “Wannabe” persona’s journey was defined through a co-creation workshop during the project GA that took place in February 2025.

“Wannabe” persona: Carla

Figure 6: “Wannabe” persona card (Catalonia)

“Proficient” persona: Carlos

	NAME Carlos	CHARACTERISATION - He is an employee of the local business association - Very proactive on the topic
	JOB POSITION Community manager	
GOALS - Increase members - Improve the governance - Seek for tools and funds	PAIN POINTS - Engagement is very demanding and he does this on top of his normal job - Lacks good arguments to convince new companies to join - Feels lost in bureaucracy	

Figure 7: “Proficient” persona card (Catalonia)

Experience map "Wannabe" persona Catalonia

STAGE	1. AWARENESS <small>(THEY REALISE THEY HAVE A PROBLEM TO SOLVE)</small>	2. CONSIDERATION <small>(THEY TRY TO FIGURE OUT IF ENERGIZE IS A GOOD SOLUTION)</small>	3. SIGN-UP <small>(THEY ENROLL IN OUR PLATFORM AND TRAININGS)</small>	4. USE <small>(THEY CARRY OUT THE TRAININGS, ONLINE AND F2F)</small>	5. ADVOCACY <small>(THEY ADVOCATE AND RECOMMEND ENERGIZE)</small>
GOALS What do they want to achieve? Why?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce energy costs Understand if joining a REC is a good deal for the company 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pick up most effective learning opportunity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Go through a smooth and fast process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start using the training ASAP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Convert neighbour enterprises to the idea of the REC
ACTIONS What steps do they take?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Search on the Web Ask local business/industry organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Check our website Search for testimonials Read through packages on offer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share internally Set up an account Sign up for specific trainings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share the account with relevant employees Engage with fellow learners Go through content Utilise FAQ or chatbot for support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommend to other companies Receives a completion certificate Receives feedback from her team Provides a testimonial on her experience
TOUCHPOINTS What/who are they interacting with?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local business/industry organisation Survey/interviews Local events Manresa Il-lumina REC Symbiosis (project partner) ICAEN (project partner) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ website ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email Live online events Live F2F events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email
PAIN POINTS What are their barriers or challenges?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The company has asbestos on the roof Afraid of REC upfront costs Unsure about who to speak to: there is not a unique point of contact Navigating renewables bureaucracy Funding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unsure ENERGIZE+ programme is a good investment of time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The first impression of the content does not meet her expectations (too little, too complicated, too simple...) Technical glitches on the platform The platform is confusing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty to follow the training if is delivered in English Who will provide support at the end of the project? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of time and rewards
OPPORTUNITIES What could be improved? What can we do for them at this stage? Which messages should we vehicle?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Build synergies with local organisations and be visible for them - e.g. UPIC (Unión de Polígonos Industriales) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide a clear outline of what they will learn, benefits and testimonials Precise the time commitment expected from their side Inform via email all the companies in industrial parks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rigorous testing of the platform before the release Incorporate feedback from user research the training contents Test UX with beta testers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide subtitles/translation Set up a responsive customer care service (email, chatbot, FAQ) Structure the programme leaving space for new/improved content towards the end 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reflect on long-term sustainability: who is going to take over the platform? Elaborate a reward for advocates of the programme (visibility, direct access to key advice/tools...)

Figure 8 "Wannabe" persona experience map (Catalonia)

Experience map "Proficient" persona Catalonia

STAGE	1. AWARENESS <small>(THEY REALISE THEY HAVE A PROBLEM TO SOLVE)</small>	2. CONSIDERATION <small>(THEY TRY TO FIGURE OUT IF ENERGIZE IS A GOOD SOLUTION)</small>	3. SIGN-UP <small>(THEY ENROLL IN OUR PLATFORM AND TRAININGS)</small>	4. USE <small>(THEY CARRY OUT THE TRAININGS, ONLINE AND F2F)</small>	5. ADVOCACY <small>(THEY ADVOCATE AND RECOMMEND ENERGIZE)</small>
GOALS What do they want to achieve? Why?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase number of members Improve the governance Identify tools and funds for managing and expanding the community 	<p>Understand if ENERGIZE+ programme is a time-effective resource and whether it can provide concrete tools</p>	<p>Go through a smooth and fast process</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start using the training ASAP Get applicable insights 	<p>Upskill other people so he doesn't have to carry all the burden</p>
ACTIONS What steps do they take?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Search on the Web Ask to administration info points Attend ICAEN events Present the community in local events with business representatives Send out newsletter/emails 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Check our website Search for testimonials Read through packages on offer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share internally Set up an account Sign up for specific trainings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invite relevant employees/colleagues Engage with fellow learners Go through content Utilise FAQ or chatbot for support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommend to other companies Receives a completion certificate Receives feedback from members Provides a testimonial on his experience
TOUCHPOINTS What/who are they interacting with?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business association Survey/interviews Local events ICAEN (project partner) Symbiosis (project partner) ESTRATS (project partner) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ website ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email Live online events Live F2F events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email
PAIN POINTS What are their barriers or challenges?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Navigating bureaucracy Not their main job, so they end up overworking Mental fatigue of convincing people Hard to convince people: there are no immediate benefits in joining the REC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unsure ENERGIZE+ programme is a good investment of time Wonders if content is for beginners Afraid that since it is an European initiative it will have little added value for the local context 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The first impression of the content does not meet his expectations (too little, too complicated, too simple...) Technical glitches on the platform The platform is confusing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty to follow the training if is delivered in English Content not adapted to his specific needs Who will provide support at the end of the project? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enrolling other people and playing the role of the ambassador is time consuming and has not material reward Unsure whether the programme will be available long-term
OPPORTUNITIES What could be improved? What can we do for them at this stage? Which messages should we vehicle?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Present ENERGIZE+ Acceleration Programme as a structured opportunity to acquire new resources and leverages for maintaining and expanding the community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide a clear outline of what they will learn, benefits and testimonials Precise the time commitment expected from their side Highlight the presence of Catalan partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rigorous testing of the platform before the release Incorporate feedback from user research the training contents Test UX with beta testers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide subtitles/translation Set up a responsive customer care service (email, chatbot, FAQ) Structure the programme leaving space for new/improved content towards the end 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reflect on long-term sustainability: who is going to take over the platform? Elaborate a reward for advocates of the programme (visibility, direct access to key contacts/tools...)

Figure 9 "Proficient" persona experience map (Catalonia)

3.1.11 Conclusions for the Catalan pilot

Cost reduction and environmental sustainability emerged as the dominant energy goals across Catalonia, with a strong interest in joining energy communities—primarily driven by the promise of economic savings. Notably, in Manresa, social motivations such as community building and knowledge exchange carry greater weight, likely bolstered by the active role of the Bufalvent business association. This strong local leadership has proven instrumental in fostering trust and mobilising participation, highlighting the importance of anchoring initiatives in existing community networks.

The energy transition is most tangibly expressed through plans to install solar panels and EV charging stations, pointing to a collective move toward energy autonomy and renewables. Yet significant barriers persist. In Manresa, administrative complexity is the chief concern, while in less established areas, the high initial investment remains the main deterrent. Across all regions, uncertainty—whether financial, procedural, or regulatory—continues to undermine confidence and delay action.

An element of reflection for ICAEN is that the administration makes efforts to maintain transparency regarding grant programmes. For instance, the status of applications and resolution outcomes for IDAE-supported industrial aid schemes is publicly available and constantly updated on their website: [ICAEN - IDAE grants for industrial efficiency](#). This transparency, while sometimes overlooked, reflects a commitment to accountability. This is an opportunity for the project to increase awareness around existing procedures and incentives.

Further challenges include widespread distrust in institutional support and energy distributors, and a major infrastructural hurdle: the prevalence of asbestos in industrial buildings, which obstructs PV deployment. Despite cost savings being a key expected benefit, most stakeholders have yet to experience them directly, reinforcing the need for clear, realistic financial roadmaps.

Importantly, there is strong demand for knowledge and capacity-building. Stakeholders acknowledge a lack of understanding around legal, technical, and organisational aspects of energy communities. Interest is particularly high in practical learning opportunities related to solar energy, batteries, governance models, and funding mechanisms, especially EU and regional support schemes. Preferred formats include live webinars and self-paced modules, complemented by individual coaching and in-person workshops.

From this landscape, two main user profiles emerge. The "Proficient" are already involved in energy communities and seek advanced insights, while the "Wannabe" are motivated beginners in need of foundational guidance and inspirational examples. Both their user journeys highlight opportunities for ENERGIZE partners to connect with umbrella organisations in energy and in industrial parks, develop modules that address local challenges and possibly in Catalan, focus the training offering around energy communities and articulate clearly the benefits of participating in the Acceleration Programme.

3.2 Valsesia Region (Italy)

Nestled in the valleys of the Sesia River, Valsesia is part of the Piedmont region in northwestern Italy. It is known for its rich natural landscapes, including alpine forests, glacial valleys, and protected areas such as the Alta Valsesia Natural Park, the highest nature reserve in Italy.

Valsesia has a historically diverse economy, with roots in textile production, metalworking, woodworking, and tourism. The textile industry flourished for decades, particularly in wool and cotton processing, but faced a decline in the late 20th century due to global competition and deindustrialisation. The region's economy also includes mechanical engineering, artisanal craftsmanship, and food production, particularly cheese-making and traditional Walser agriculture. Tourism is a key economic driver, with ski resorts like Alagna Valsesia, renowned for freeride skiing, and a growing interest in outdoor sports, ecotourism, and cultural heritage tourism.

3.2.1 Energy context and regulation

Italy's energy mix remains heavily reliant on natural gas, but renewable sources—particularly solar, hydro, wind, and biomass—have steadily increased their share. Italy's Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) outlines a roadmap to reach 30% renewable energy in gross final consumption by 2030, alongside improvements in energy efficiency and grid modernisation (PNIEC Italy 2024). The country has also adopted the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), which allocates substantial funds to accelerate the green transition, with a focus on decentralised energy systems, smart grids, and the creation of energy communities. Zooming into the Piedmont region, the energy mix reflects a **strong reliance on hydropower**, which covers about 60% of the region's renewable electricity production (*Re_piemonte2022_dgr.Pdf*, n.d.). As of 2021, Piedmont had more than 1,000 operational hydroelectric plants, alongside a growing number of solar PV installations, particularly in the provinces of Cuneo, Alessandria, and Novara (the latter being the province of Valsesia). The Regional Energy and Environmental Plan (PEAR) sets out goals for a 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions by 2030, improved energy efficiency in public infrastructure, and increased deployment of renewables, especially in mountain areas like Valsesia where decentralised production is viable (*Piano Energetico Ambientale Regionale (PEAR)*, n.d.). Piedmont has also allocated funds from the PNRR to develop smart grids, install renewable heat networks, and support energy communities through technical assistance and targeted grants.

In Italy, the regulation of energy communities is defined by Legislative Decree No. 199/2021, which transposes the European RED II Directive (2018/2001). This legislation establishes:

Who can participate: natural and legal persons, condominiums, SMEs, public entities, religious associations, and research institutions.

The legal model: communities can be established as cooperatives, associations, or other recognised legal forms.

Available incentives: contributions proportional to the power of the installation and the amount of shared energy.

Starting in 2025, additional benefits are planned to encourage the creation of new energy communities, including tax breaks for businesses investing in these initiatives and favorable financing conditions for citizens who wish to join.

3.2.2 Energy transition and energy cooperation efforts in Valsesia

In recent years, Valsesia has been actively working towards a sustainable energy transition. In 2023 the "Unione Montana dei comuni della Valsesia" (representing all the municipalities of the area) published a feasibility study for energy cooperation, which identified the most promising areas for public building installations. The feasibility study has been limited to the municipalities below 5000 inhabitants, excluding Varallo and Borgosesia. As a consequence, together with 10 mayors of the valley municipalities, in 2024 the Quarona mayor and president of "Unione Montana dei comuni della Valsesia" established the "CER

valesia società cooperativa impresa sociale”, hereby defined as REC Valsesia, as a legal entity to drive the co-creation process.

The REC limit lies below the primary cabin substations areas within the valley, as shown in Figure 11 below where AC001E01438, 39, 50 and 51 are the one included in the community geographical scope.

Figure 10: GSE primary cabin substations

Several private enterprises and private citizens already requested to join the cooperative to benefit from the PNRR fund for the installation of PV systems devoted to REC Valsesia. The general assembly of the REC Valsesia will establish the managing scheme and the remuneration rules for their members. Several enterprises that showed interested in the project, in municipalities above 5000 inhabitants, are looking for alternative financial incentives and are interested to join the REC Valsesia as consumers. While the legislative framework is looking to expand the limit for the PNRR fund for renewable systems installed in areas below 30000 inhabitants, the renewable energy projects are still developing. The region benefits from hydropower resources, thanks to its mountainous geography and abundant water sources. Some privately owned hydropower plants showed interest in joining the REC Valsesia and benefit from the incentive created by the energy shared between members. The local government and energy cooperatives are promoting small-scale hydroelectric plants and solar energy solutions for alpine communities. Italy’s evolving legal framework on energy communities is expected to support local initiatives, fostering greater energy independence and sustainability.

ENERGIZE will look at the industry parks located nearby Varallo and Borgosesia, the two mayor cities of the Valsesia regions. The Roccapietra industrial park, located near Varallo, serves as a relatively cohesive cluster of enterprises actively involved in the energy community initiative, whereas other businesses in the more scattered across Borgosesia area—linked to a different primary cabin—are joining with less coordination and mixed levels of engagement. The smaller enterprises in the upper valley are not officially part of any industrial park but are still eligible to join as a member of the REC Valsesia.

3.2.3 Stakeholder mapping

The actors identified in Valsesia for co-creation can be grouped in the following categories:

- Industrial parks and associations
- Financial entities

- Energy businesses (operators, distributors, utilities, consultancies)
- Public administration
- Energy communities
- Individual industries in industrial parks

Stakeholder	Type	Relevance
Zona Industriale Roccapietra	Industrial parks and associations	The alpine region of Valsesia host several factories that could catalyse the REC Valsesia thanks to higher consumption and significant financial benefit from participating in a shared self-consumption scheme. They will be involved to answer the survey and as beneficiaries of the Acceleration Programme.
Zona industrial Via Luigi Zignone		
Zona Artigianale Via Manifatture		
Zona Artigianale Via Valduggia		
Zona Industrial Via Cesare Battisti		
Zona Industriale Bivio del Rondò		
Zona Industriale Spazio della Cremosina		
Zona Industriale Corso Vercelli		
Consorzio San Giulio		
Confindustria		
Unioncamere		
Ecomill	Financial entities and investors	They could cover part of the financial requirements of the investment and support the capacity building of the Acceleration Programme
Ener2Crowd		
Fondazione Compagnia di San Paolo		
Tecnoverde	Energy businesses	They will be involved as ambassadors and partners of the Acceleration Programme.
Unione montana dei comuni della Valsesia	Public administration and energy agencies	They will be involved as ambassadors and partners of the Acceleration Programme, that can support the reach of their energy targets.
Associazione Monte Rosa Foreste		
Ente di gestione dei sacri monti		
GAL Terre del Sesia		
Ente di gestione delle Aree protette della Valsesia		
CORDAR Valsesia		
Municipality of Quarona		

Municipality of Varallo	Energy communities	They will be involved to answer the survey and as beneficiaries of the Acceleration Programme.
Municipality of Borgosesia		
Renewable energy community of Valsesia		
Renewable energy community of Postua		
Renewable energy community of Guardabosone	Individual industries	They will be involved to answer the survey and as beneficiaries of the Acceleration Programme.
HAL service		
Gallazzini		
Loropiana		
Valvomec		
Tosi		
Turlo		
Arfino		
Rubinetterie Ritmonio Srl		
Model Plastic		
Lanificio Reggiani		
Maestrini SRL		
Rubinetteria Condor		
HAL service		
Informatica data system		

Table 2 Stakeholder mapping Valsesia

Stakeholders Map Val Sesia

Figure 11 Stakeholder map (Valsesia)

3.2.4 Interviewees' profile

The following stakeholders were interviewed in the Valsesia area:

- CEO of ICT company
- Energy managers for the regional General Confederation of Italian Industry (Confindustria)
- President of the Valsesia Municipalities Association (Unione Comunità Montana Valsesia)
- Association representing the local forestry sector
- Architectural cultural heritage preservation organisation

3.2.5 Survey respondents' profile

Survey participation in the Valsesia pilot was limited, despite repeated outreach efforts to engage potential respondents. Only thirteen responses were collected, of which just eight were fully completed. This small sample size restricted the depth of analysis, preventing the creation of detailed respondent profiles or the extraction of meaningful quantitative insights.

Nevertheless, the responses gathered align with several themes identified in the expert interviews. While not statistically representative, they offer anecdotal reinforcement of certain qualitative findings—for instance, a strong interest in energy communities, the challenge of navigating complex group decision-making, and a common practice of installing solar panels for self-consumption.

Given these constraints, the survey results are shared here in a purely illustrative manner. They should be interpreted with caution and viewed as complementary to the more robust insights drawn from interviews and desk research. These limitations also highlight the need for more tailored engagement approaches and simplified survey tools when working with businesses and semi-industrial actors in future research phases.

3.2.6 Priorities and motivations for the energy transition

3.2.6.1 *Results from interviews*

Stakeholders view energy communities (CERs, “Comunità Energetiche Rinnovabili”) positively and express a **general willingness to engage in initiatives that benefit both the environment and the local community**. Rather than seeing CERs as traditional energy providers, they understand them as collective entities fostering shared responsibility and local cooperation.

Some stakeholders, for instance, mentioned plans to use structural funds to install a solar farm on a rooftop—demonstrating a concrete intention to contribute to the energy transition at the local level. According to Confindustria, companies that have already invested in photovoltaic systems typically **prioritise self-consumption**, as their operations use most of the energy they produce. This is particularly true for the textile industry, which operates even on weekends, limiting the potential for energy accumulation. In contrast, sectors like metal manufacturing, which tend to close on weekends, may show greater interest in sharing surplus energy.

The feasibility study for establishing a CER in the region was driven by the dual goals of environmental preservation and local energy production and consumption. The community created is structured as a **cooperative that aims to involve both citizens and businesses**. Plans are in place to create a one-stop-shop (OSS) for providing accessible information and guidance. Despite minimal promotional efforts, at the time of the interview the launch of the initiative already gathered interest from around 40 individuals. The local biomass value chain, fuelled by surrounding forests, shows strong confidence in its ability to meet a significant share of local energy demand, particularly through a combination of biomass and hydroelectric sources. A recent public tender supported the transition from outdated boilers to newer, biomass-fuelled models.

Local organisations focused on promoting cultural heritage also see the energy transition—particularly through the use of biomass—as an opportunity to drive territorial development. These actors are integrating renewable energy and circular economy principles into their broader strategies for sustainable regional growth.

Results from survey

All respondents reported having already invested in renewable energy infrastructure, mainly thermal or photovoltaic solar panels and electric vehicle (EV) charging stations. These installations were typically financed through a combination of public grants and private capital. Looking ahead to the next five years, there is a shared intention among respondents to further **expand their solar energy capacity**, either by adding new installations or upgrading existing systems.

When asked about their motivations for investing in energy-related projects, respondents consistently identified **cost reduction** as the primary driver. This financial motivation was closely followed by environmental considerations, such as **enhancing sustainability and increasing the share of renewables** in their energy mix.

Importantly, all respondents expressed a **clear interest in joining an energy community**. Their motivations for doing so mirrored those that guide their energy investments: lowering energy costs and improving environmental performance. In addition, two further motivations emerged. First, respondents view energy communities as a potential buffer against volatility in energy markets, offering greater stability in pricing over time. Second, they see participation as a strategic move that aligns with long-term organisational planning.

3.2.7 Barriers for energy cooperation

3.2.7.1 *Results from interviews*

A number of practical, regulatory, and systemic barriers are limiting the development of energy communities (CERs) in the region, despite growing interest in renewable energy.

Technical and regulatory constraints. One rooftop alone could produce up to 2 MW of solar energy, but current regulations restrict installations to 700 kW. Moreover, the equipment must be sourced from within the EU, significantly increasing costs compared to cheaper alternatives available from China.

Industry readiness. Confindustria points out that while CERs are a hot topic, tangible progress remains scarce. Key barriers include outdated grid infrastructure, the urgent need to upgrade HVAC systems, and a general lack of trust in collective models. A local initiative, Consorzio San Giulio, has managed collective energy purchasing for over 25 years, but this effort has remained focused on cost savings, with limited attention to environmental or social goals.

Although there is widespread interest in renewables, this does not necessarily translate into enthusiasm for collective initiatives. Many companies perceive the decision-making processes within CERs as lengthy and complex, with unclear or insufficient benefits to justify the effort.

Geographic and structural limitations. The region's distance from major urban centres puts it at a disadvantage in terms of accessing technical skills and innovative technologies. The regulatory environment is perceived as unstable, with frequent rule changes and excessive bureaucracy. For example, a company was required to replace pre-installed pipe insulation glue with a fireproof version to comply with new regulations—an anecdote reflecting the costly and time-consuming nature of compliance.

Financial and administrative burdens. Stakeholders acknowledge that renewable energy development is largely subsidised by taxpayers through incentives. They hope that energy communities can help ease the burden of high electricity costs and improve the competitiveness of local industry. However, managing Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) is seen as highly complex, pointing to the urgent need for automation through AI or dedicated digital platforms.

Information and communication gaps. There is a significant lack of accessible information and clear communication regarding CERs. Administrative procedures are often time-consuming, opaque, and difficult to navigate. This creates a barrier both for businesses and citizens willing to engage.

Biomass challenges. In the biomass value chain, stakeholders note a decline in wood quality, with a large share of material rendered unusable. Logistics for transporting wood are also challenging and costly. On a political level, public administrations are urged to do more to communicate effectively with citizens about energy and transition issues.

Cultural heritage limitations. In areas with historical protected buildings, regulations prohibit the installation of photovoltaic systems, further limiting renewable energy deployment in parts of the region.

3.2.7.2 *Results from survey*

The most commonly perceived barrier to engaging in energy communities is the **complexity of aligning administrative and operational procedures with other members**. Respondents expressed concern about the challenges of coordinating effectively across diverse actors, each with their own internal processes, decision-making timelines, and operational constraints. This concern is compounded by a fear that members may hold diverging goals and priorities, making it difficult to establish a shared vision or common ground for collaboration.

In addition to coordination challenges, respondents also identified a **lack of internal resources**, such as limited time, insufficient staff capacity and lack of expertise, as a significant obstacle.

3.2.8 Lessons learned from existing energy cooperation initiatives

3.2.8.1 *Results from interviews*

Stakeholders observed that energy initiatives tend to be more successful when led or strongly supported by municipalities. **Local governments provide a sense of legitimacy** and alignment with the common good, which helps motivate citizens and businesses to participate.

The **feasibility study** played a crucial role by offering concrete data and a shared vision on which to base the project. However, both public servants and businesses highlighted the need for transparency—particularly regarding how the community is managed and how economic benefits are distributed.

The establishment of the Energy Community (CER) under the *Unione Montana* was made possible thanks to the ability of several municipalities to unite around a common objective. This inter-municipal collaboration emerged as a key success factor for moving from ambition to implementation.

3.2.9 Skill gaps and training formats

3.2.9.1 *Results from interviews*

Stakeholders expressed a strong interest in gaining knowledge across several areas related to the energy transition:

Energy production sources: High interest in solar and biomass-based systems.

Energy communities: A need for practical guidance on organisational and business models, regulatory frameworks, success stories, and effective communication strategies.

Innovative financing mechanisms: Curiosity about alternative financing solutions such as Energy Performance Contracts (EPC), crowdfunding, and revolving funds.

Policy awareness: Some interest was also noted in understanding energy generation and efficiency policies, especially those that impact local or regional planning.

Participants suggested a mix of formats to accommodate different learning preferences and schedules, primarily webinars, complemented by occasional in-person workshops. One participant recommended a repository of training materials (e.g. videos, slide decks, guides) to be made available online, allowing users to access and learn at their own pace.

3.2.9.2 *Results from survey*

Participants declared a basic grasp of the key concepts related to energy cooperation, although they did not consider themselves experts in the field. This self-assessment reflects a level of awareness that can serve as a foundation for further capacity-building. Notably, **all respondents had taken part in at least one training session or public presentation related to energy communities** during 2024, which confirms that the topic is of growing interest and perceived relevance among stakeholders.

Among the technical topics, battery storage emerged as the most engaging and frequently mentioned area of interest. This was followed by a general curiosity about the fundamentals of energy communities, solar energy systems, and combined heat and power (CHP) technologies.

Within the broader topic of energy communities, respondents expressed a strong demand for more information and guidance on **organisational models**. This was closely followed by interest in viable **business models** and the underlying **principles of producing and sharing energy at the community level**.

In terms of funding opportunities, European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF) and Regional Operational Programmes were cited as the most relevant and sought-after sources of support.

When it comes to energy policy, the **national level** was consistently viewed as more relevant and influential than the international or EU levels.

Finally, regarding preferred training formats, participants showed a clear interest in **online webinars and study visits**.

3.2.10 User personas and user experience maps

Based on the data collected in Valsesia, two key user personas emerge that reflect the local dynamics around energy cooperation. The first is the **“Lone Ranger”**—typically a representative of a local industry that has already invested in photovoltaic systems for self-consumption but remains sceptical about collective initiatives. This profile values independence, efficiency, and return on investment, and tends to perceive energy communities as slow, bureaucratic, and potentially risky due to unclear governance and benefit-sharing mechanisms.

The second is the **“Community Manager”**—a representative of public administration, umbrella organisations, or local development bodies who actively promote energy cooperation as a tool for territorial cohesion, environmental transition, and social innovation. This persona plays a connector role, helping align diverse stakeholders around shared goals, and is particularly interested in frameworks for PA-industry collaboration, success stories from other regions, and tools to communicate the value of energy communities to broader audiences.

This duality reflects the tension—and the opportunity—within Valsesia’s energy transition: bridging individual initiative with collective action. Recognising and addressing the needs, concerns, and motivations of both personas will be crucial to designing effective engagement strategies and tailored capacity-building formats. These insights build on ongoing fieldwork in the area and contribute to a more grounded understanding of what drives or hinders participation in energy communities in mountainous and semi-industrialised contexts.

Figure 12 "Lone Ranger" persona card (Valsesia)

Figure 13 "Community Manager" persona card (Valsesia)

Experience map "Lone Ranger" Val Sesia

STAGE	1. AWARENESS <small>(THEY REALISE THEY HAVE A PROBLEM TO SOLVE)</small>	2. CONSIDERATION <small>(THEY TRY TO FIGURE OUT IF ENERGIZE IS A GOOD SOLUTION)</small>	3. SIGN-UP <small>(THEY ENROLL IN OUR PLATFORM AND TRAININGS)</small>	4. USE <small>(THEY CARRY OUT THE TRAININGS, ONLINE AND F2F)</small>	5. ADVOCACY <small>(THEY ADVOCATE AND RECOMMEND ENERGIZE)</small>
GOALS What do they want to achieve? Why?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce energy costs Increase the share of renewables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pick-up most effective learning opportunity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Go through a smooth and fast process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start using the trainings ASAP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Convert neighbour enterprises to the idea of REC
ACTIONS What steps do they take?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ask local business/industry association Search on the Web 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Check ENERGIZE+ website Search for testimonials Read through our training offer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share internally Set up an account Sign up for specific trainings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engage with fellow learners Share the account with/ invite relevant employees Utilise FAQ or chatbot support Go through content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommend to other companies Receives a completion certificate Receives feedback from his team
TOUCHPOINTS What/who are they interacting with?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local business/industry organisation Local events Engreen (project partner) Survey/interviews 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ website ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform Live online events Live F2F events Contact email 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform
PAIN POINTS What are their barriers or challenges?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Afraid of upfront costs and bureaucracy Worried about the impact of energy expenses on business sustainability Doesn't trust collaboration between companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Afraid of getting trapped in any obligations Unsure E+ is a good time investment Lack of trust in EU projects Doesn't understand E+ offer Suspicious of lack of involvement of LRA or public authorities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Elderly participant (low tech literacy) Bad internet connection Time consuming (may easily drop out) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Language barriers Difficulty in understanding impact and applicability for their business Not enough interaction on the platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time consuming and little incentives to advocate for the training By showcasing my experience I give my competitive advantage away
OPPORTUNITIES What could be improved? What can we do for them at this stage? Which messages should we vehicle?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highlight additional benefits of cooperation and public incentives Increase general knowledge on renewable sources Showcase the impact of cooperation in other territories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide clear and concrete outline of what they will learn and ROI Precise time commitment expected from their side Provide orientation services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> User friendly sign-up process and interface Professional aesthetics Involve a large number of companies Provide visibility to companies which sign up 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide modules on economic return of energy coop. (e.g. with simulations) Present training as means to upskill C-level team in accessing RES financing and partnerships 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local or regional ambassadors Case studies of successful "students" Provide means to promote the participant companies

Figure 14 "Lone Ranger" persona experience map (Valsesia)

Experience map "Community Manager" persona Val Sesia

STAGE	1. AWARENESS <small>(THEY REALISE THEY HAVE A PROBLEM TO SOLVE)</small>	2. CONSIDERATION <small>(THEY TRY TO FIGURE OUT IF ENERGIZE IS A GOOD SOLUTION)</small>	3. SIGN-UP <small>(THEY ENROLL IN OUR PLATFORM AND TRAININGS)</small>	4. USE <small>(THEY CARRY OUT THE TRAININGS, ONLINE AND F2F)</small>	5. ADVOCACY <small>(THEY ADVOCATE AND RECOMMEND ENERGIZE)</small>
GOALS What do they want to achieve? Why?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create an energy community Get support to go from the feasibility study to implementation Seek for tools and funds 	<p>Understand if ENERGIZE+ programme is a time-effective resource and whether it can provide concrete tools</p>	<p>Go through a smooth and fast process</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start using the training ASAP Get applicable insights 	<p>Upskill other people so he doesn't have to carry all the burden</p>
ACTIONS What steps do they take?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Search on the Web Attend local events Present the community project in local events with business representatives Send out newsletter/emails 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Check our website Search for testimonials Read through packages on offer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share internally Set up an account Sign up for specific trainings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invite relevant employees/colleagues Engage with fellow learners Go through content Utilise FAQ or chatbot for support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommend to other municipalities Receives a completion certificate Receives feedback from members Provides a testimonial on his experience
TOUCHPOINTS What/who are they interacting with?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unione Comunità Montana Valsesia Survey/interviews Local events Engreen (project partner) Confindustria 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ website ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email Live online events Live F2F events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email
PAIN POINTS What are their barriers or challenges?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Navigating bureaucracy Not their main task, so they end up overworking Mental fatigue of convincing people Hard to convince people: there are no immediate benefits in joining the REC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unsure ENERGIZE+ programme is a good investment of time Wonders if content is OK for his level of energy literacy Doubts the programme has enough elements about the Italian context 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The first impression of the content does not meet his expectations (too little, too complicated, too simple...) Technical glitches on the platform The platform is confusing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty to follow the training if is delivered in English Content not adapted to his specific needs Who will provide support at the end of the project? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enrolling other people and playing the role of the ambassador is time consuming and has no material reward Unsure whether the programme will be available long-term
OPPORTUNITIES What could be improved? What can we do for them at this stage? Which messages should we vehicle?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Present ENERGIZE+ Acceleration Programme as a structured opportunity to learn how to launch a community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide a clear outline of what they will learn, benefits and testimonials Precise the time commitment expected from their side Highlight the presence of Italian partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rigorous testing of the platform before the release Incorporate feedback from user research the training contents Test UX with beta testers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide subtitles/translation Set up a responsive customer care service (email, chatbot, FAQ) Structure the programme leaving space for new/improved content towards the end 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reflect on long-term sustainability: who is going to take over the platform? Elaborate a reward for advocates of the programme (visibility, direct access to key contacts/tools...)

Figure 15 "Community Manager" persona experience map (Valsesia)

3.2.11 Conclusions for the Italian Pilot

The Italian pilot in the Valsesia region highlighted a landscape characterised by **strong interest in renewable energy and a growing awareness of energy communities** (CERs), yet also marked by notable challenges in translating this interest into collective action. Through a combination of expert interviews and a limited survey, the pilot captured the perspectives of both institutional actors and local businesses, revealing a complex interplay of motivations, barriers, and enabling factors.

Stakeholders demonstrated a genuine willingness to contribute to the energy transition, particularly through **investments in self-consumption** and the integration of renewables like solar and biomass. The CER initiative spearheaded by the Unione Montana shows promising signs of traction, with early interest from both citizens and companies, and a clear alignment with local development goals. The presence of local actors such as forestry associations and heritage organisations further underscores the potential for a place-based, multi-sectoral approach to energy cooperation.

At the same time, the pilot surfaced several **structural and cultural obstacles**. Businesses, especially in the industrial sector, expressed scepticism towards collective energy initiatives due to **concerns around complexity, unclear benefits, and governance challenges**. Regulatory constraints, administrative burdens, and limited access to technical resources also hinder the scalability of renewable energy projects. These barriers are particularly pronounced in remote and mountainous regions like Valsesia, where logistical and infrastructural limitations further complicate implementation.

Despite these challenges, the pilot revealed two distinct user profiles that offer a roadmap for future engagement: the “Lone Ranger,” focused on individual efficiency and return on investment, and the “Community Manager,” oriented towards territorial cohesion and collaboration. **Bridging these two mindsets will be essential to unlock the full potential of energy communities in the region.**

Capacity-building emerged as a key area for intervention. Stakeholders expressed a **need for clearer information, practical guidance on organisational models, and access to tailored training resources**. The preference for flexible learning formats such as webinars and on-demand materials points to the importance of designing accessible and user-friendly educational content.

Ultimately, while enthusiasm for renewable energy is evident, fostering durable collective models will require support targeted at simplifying complex information and providing guidance on organisational models.

3.3 Zlín Region (Czech Republic)

Zlín is situated in the valley of the Dřevnice Stream, and it is the country's fourth smallest region, bordered by Slovakia to the east, where the White Carpathians form part of the border. Zlín is home to a diverse set of industries including plastics and rubber, chemical production, mechanical engineering, footwear and leather, ICT and electronics, buildings and construction as well as food processing (*Business Structure:: Catalogue of Companies in the Zlín Region*, n.d.).

The region faced a significant GDP decline in the late 1990s due to structural changes in traditional industries, particularly the footwear and aircraft industries which had formerly achieved international recognition during Soviet times for their quality, were affected. The 2009 economic crisis led to a 7.5% decline in real GDP, particularly affecting export-oriented manufacturing sectors. Economic viability is thus a major concern for the region's industry owners (*Economic Overview:: Catalogue of Companies in the Zlín Region*, n.d.).

3.3.1 Energy context and regulation

The State energy policy of the Czech Republic identifies 5 key priorities: balanced energy mix; savings and efficiency; infrastructure and international cooperation; research, development and innovation; energy security (State-Energy-Policy-2015-EN.Pdf, n.d.). In 2024, the Czech Republic adopted legislation on energy communities, establishing two categories: Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs). While the law outlines the core principles of both definitions, it lacks detailed regulations to create an enabling framework that would allow these communities to participate in the energy market on equal terms. Additionally, no assessment has been conducted to identify the barriers or potential for the development of RECs. Although financial support for renewables is available through the national Recovery and Resilience Plan and the Modernisation Fund, the national renewable energy support scheme does not include targeted measures for energy communities (Czech Republic - REScoop, n.d.). EAZK reports of one call for energy communities, but it was targeting municipalities and provided support for the preparatory phase. Provisional solutions are not particularly advantageous for energy communities because they only allow for a static method of electricity distribution. However, the provisional solution is set to be replaced by the final version from July 1, 2026. According to an informal agreement, the final solution is expected to allow for both dynamic and hybrid electricity distribution (UKEN | Unie Komunitní Energetiky, n.d.). In April 2025, the Czech government approved a draft law designed to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy sources (RES). This legislative initiative marks a significant step forward in advancing the country's energy transition, particularly by streamlining permitting processes for solar and wind projects. A central feature of the draft law is the creation of "acceleration zones"—designated areas where the construction of renewable energy installations will benefit from simplified and expedited permitting procedures. While the proposal introduces several promising measures aligned with EU directives—most notably RED III and the RePowerEU plan—it also exposes key shortcomings, especially in areas such as public participation, community energy inclusion, and grid capacity planning (Legislative Developments in the Czech Republic, n.d.).

3.3.2 Energy transition and energy cooperation efforts in the Zlín region

In the Zlín region, energy community projects are at an early stage. Nevertheless, there is progress towards encouraging the adaptation of renewable energy, with ongoing efforts to create the necessary infrastructure and support systems. The Czech Republic has recently passed legislation on energy communities, which will further enhance the move towards more sustainable energy production and usage ("Zlín's Comprehensive Approach to the Energy Transition," n.d.). The region has also launched more energy projects and the Energy Agency of the Zlín Region (EAZK) is leading efforts to implement sustainable energy policies. The EU-funded project [ePlanet](#) has recently conducted a capacity-building

program for Zlín Region comprising a set of 8 activities, including technical trainings and content-focused sessions on governance, innovative financing for solar energy communities, and buildings. Additionally, two extra internal training sessions were organized by EAZK to provide technical sessions in the pilot territory. All activities were conducted in Czech and in person, involving 340 participants from various backgrounds (*ePLANET-17th-Press-Release-EN-Zlin-Region-CBA.Pdf*, n.d.). Because of the early stages of energy cooperation in Czech Republic, ENERGIZE aims to expand previous EU-funded training efforts and demonstrate the benefits of cooperative energy models in industrial areas.

3.3.3 Stakeholder mapping

The actors identified in Zlín Region for co-creation can be grouped in the following categories:

- Industrial parks and associations
- Individual industries in industrial parks
- Public administration (especially municipalities)
- Energy businesses (operators, distributors, utilities, consultancies)

Stakeholder	Type	Relevance
Holešov	Industrial parks and associations	They will be involved in survey and interviews, contributing to assess the training needs; later, they will be involved as beneficiaries of the Acceleration Programme
	Individual industries	They will be involved to answer the survey and as beneficiaries of the Acceleration Programme.
Municipalities	Public administration	They will be involved as ambassadors and partners of the Acceleration Programme, which can support the reach of their energy targets.
Teplo Zlin (distributor)	Energy actors	They will be involved in the preparation of technical feasibility plans/prospects to provide technical expertise for the Acceleration Programme
EG.D (distributor)		
ČEZ (distributor)		
AH energy (operation and maintenance)		
BTH Slavicin (supplier)		
EDC Energy Data Center		

Table 3 Stakeholder mapping Zlín Region

Stakeholders Map Zlín Region

Figure 16 Stakeholder map (Zlín Region)

3.3.4 Interviewees' profile

The following stakeholders were interviewed in the Zlín area:

- Representative of Zlín Regional Investment Agency (ZRIA)
- Representative of municipal company operating the heating system in Slavičín
- Representative of the regional administration
- Representative of a company specialised in the operation, maintenance, and repair of energy infrastructure and utility networks
- Mayor of a town and councillor in the regional administration

3.4 Survey respondents' profile

The Czech pilot received 38 survey responses, of which 30 were fully completed.

Most respondents are based in the Zlín region, in areas such as the industrial zones of Holešov, Otrokovice, Uherský Brod, Slavičín, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlín Přiluky, Areál Svit and Zlín Přiluky. A few individual answers came from Central Moravia (Zlín is in Eastern Moravia), the Liberec Region and the Capital Prague.

Participants are either representatives of **companies with more than 30 employees (26%)** or of **local public authorities (26%)**, followed by industrial SMEs (13%). **The private companies surveyed operate across a wide range of sectors**, including plastics processing, the food industry, photovoltaic systems, construction, electronic communications and IT, mechanical engineering, district heating, automotive, quality control, the aviation industry, heat production and distribution, and local energy solutions (buildings, energy sources, and renewable energy sources – RES).

Public sector participants are primarily involved in the management of municipal assets, investment in public infrastructure, education, social services, culture, and general municipal administration.

In terms of roles, **60% of respondents are CEOs or managing directors**, 17% are maintenance engineers or technicians, and 13% are energy managers.

Photovoltaic panels are the most common renewable energy installation (65%), followed by **batteries and district heating systems, each reported by 39%** of respondents. Solar thermal panels are used by 26%, and 13% have electric vehicle (EV) charging stations. Notably, 17% of respondents report having no renewable energy installations, while 8% use combined heat and power (CHP) systems.

Regarding financing, **installations were funded through a combination of own resources (72%), and 68% grants**.

The most **energy-consuming assets identified are HVAC systems (61%) and industrial machinery (40%)**. The main energy sources are electricity from the grid (46%) and natural gas (36%).

3.4.1 Priorities and motivations for the energy transition

3.4.1.1 *Results from interviews*

In the Zlín Region, the energy transition is shaped by a **strong economic rationale**, with environmental benefits acknowledged but considered secondary. Across municipalities and industrial zones, motivations revolve around reducing operational costs, improving self-sufficiency, and enhancing energy efficiency—particularly in response to fluctuating energy prices and evolving regulatory landscapes.

A hybrid approach is being implemented in some areas, combining traditional energy distribution with photovoltaic (PV) systems installed on the rooftops of industrial buildings. One interviewee noted that while there is potential to expand the use of excess heat—such as supplying it to the nearby town of Holešov—the infrastructural requirements (e.g., determining pipeline routes) remain unplanned, as current urban development frameworks date back to 2019, when district heating was not deemed necessary in the area.

Immediate **investment priorities focus on pragmatic upgrades** such as improved lighting for industrial halls, repairs to boiler rooms, and the refurbishment of windows and garages—all aimed at improving energy efficiency and cost control.

In Slavičín, the municipal company BTH operates a 130 kW PV system. Initially, the goal was to sell electricity back to the grid, but this strategy proved economically unsustainable as electricity prices dropped from CZK 3.5 to CZK 1 per kWh. The company now faces the challenge of allocating overhead costs between heat and electricity. Selling more electricity leads to a higher share of personnel costs being assigned to heat, thereby increasing heating expenses.

Battery storage has been considered, but there is uncertainty around whether it could be located in the boiler room. If so, the costs might be treated as part of the heating budget, potentially complicating compliance with regulated heat pricing. The Energy Regulatory Office safeguards heat prices, but not electricity, introducing further financial unpredictability.

Alternative strategies such as using electricity in electric boilers were explored but deemed too costly. The focus has shifted to heat pumps, which offer a more favourable energy conversion ratio (1 kWh of electricity produces 3 kWh of heat).

3.4.1.2 *Results from survey*

Respondents were allowed to select multiple options when indicating their planned energy-related actions, goals, and motivations.

In terms of installation plans for **the next five years, 82% of respondents intend to install photovoltaic (PV) systems**. Batteries and EV charging stations were each selected by 39% of respondents, followed by district heating (22%) and heat pumps (17%).

Cost reduction emerged as the most common energy-related goal, selected by 82% of respondents. Other frequently mentioned goals include the adoption of renewable energy sources (52%), achieving energy autonomy (30%), and enhancing sustainability (30%).

A majority (68%) expressed interest in joining an energy community. Among these, **the leading motivation is reducing energy costs (88%)**, followed by **energy security (56%)**, **access to innovation** through collective investment in new technologies (56%), and **collaboration opportunities** with other businesses (56%).

Other motivations include taking a long-term strategic perspective (50%), risk mitigation (44%), supporting economic growth (37%), taking advantage of regulatory incentives (31%), and contributing to sustainability goals (31%).

3.4.2 Barriers for energy cooperation

3.4.2.1 *Results from interviews*

Despite growing interest in renewable energy and local self-sufficiency, multiple systemic, technical, and financial barriers continue to hinder energy cooperation efforts in the Zlín Region.

One of the main challenges lies in the physical state of buildings owned by regional companies. Many suffer from structural issues such as inadequate roof insulation, defective roof construction, and insufficient load-bearing capacity—making them unsuitable for photovoltaic (PV) installations without substantial renovation. A proposed 100 kW PV project, for example, has been delayed due to the small size of available subsidies, which are insufficient to cover necessary roof repairs, lightning protection systems, and the PV installation itself. As a result, the project is not currently economically viable, and stakeholders are waiting for more favourable financial conditions. **In the long term, photovoltaic-covered parking is being considered as an alternative.**

Energy cooperation is further complicated by **fragmented responsibility and accounting**. Tenants of industrial buildings typically manage their own energy procurement, buying electricity individually. Moreover, the separate accounting for heat and electricity creates financial and regulatory complexity that discourages integrated energy planning or joint investment models.

On the policy and infrastructure side, the picture is equally challenging. Public perception is a barrier—citizens often fail to see the economic value in collective energy solutions, in part due to **entrenched distribution objectives that favour centralised models**. Allocation of costs and benefits, especially when savings depend on unpredictable weather, adds further uncertainty.

Local Distribution Systems (LDS), while present in the region, are not yet "smart" and continue to face regulatory compliance challenges—especially around requirements like reactive power compensation. Basic long-term infrastructure investments, such as the renewal of transformer stations, are either lacking or underfunded. **The broader policy environment suffers from legislative instability** and frequent regulatory changes, discouraging long-term planning and trust in the system.

Political distrust and economic uncertainty—amplified by misinformation and recent crises—undermine broader cooperation. Current subsidy schemes are often misaligned with local needs, offering poor conditions that disincentivise participation.

Previous attempts at energy sharing, such as those explored in Slavičín, have encountered geographic and infrastructural limitations. The cost and complexity of setting up dedicated cables to potential partners, combined with seasonal limitations in consumption (e.g. schools closing during summer), has rendered such projects unfeasible. Even new municipal buildings equipped with photovoltaics produce little surplus electricity, making them unattractive for shared use. Institutions like hospitals could offer more consistent demand, but existing gas infrastructure presents another retrofit challenge.

In sum, the path to cooperative, community-based energy solutions is obstructed by a combination of poor building conditions, fragmented management, insufficient infrastructure, regulatory hurdles, and a lack of trust in the stability and fairness of national and local support mechanisms.

3.4.2.2 *Results from survey*

Respondents were invited to indicate all barriers they perceive as relevant to their organisation's energy transition and potential participation in an energy community.

The most frequently cited barrier was the **complexity of administrative and operational procedures, selected by 74% of respondents**. This highlights a widespread concern about bureaucratic hurdles and the effort required to navigate regulations and implement energy solutions.

An **uncertain return on investment (ROI) was reported as a barrier by 48% of respondents**, reflecting apprehension about the financial viability and payback time of energy-related projects.

Limited flexibility and autonomy in decision-making was a concern for 44% of participants, indicating that internal governance structures or external constraints may inhibit the adoption of energy innovations.

Upfront investment costs were identified as a barrier by 43% of respondents, alongside technical limitations, such as insufficient infrastructure or in-house expertise (43%). An equal share (43%) also pointed to the difficulty of aligning goals and priorities between potential community members and the inability to allocate sufficient internal human resources to manage or support energy initiatives.

Additional barriers include concerns about cybersecurity (30%), the perceived lack of public incentives or support schemes (22%), and the insufficient reliability of renewable energy sources (26%), suggesting a need for improved communication, technical guarantees, and financial support to build trust and capacity.

3.4.3 Lessons learned from local energy cooperation initiatives

3.4.3.1 *Results from interviews*

One key insight is the need to closely align photovoltaic (PV) development with self-consumption strategies. Under current market and regulatory conditions, **exporting electricity to the grid is often economically unviable. Therefore, future PV installations should prioritise consumption on-site**, maximising the value of the generated energy and minimising dependence on external infrastructure.

Another lesson relates to the design of energy sharing schemes. To make energy sharing feasible, **it is crucial to exclude traditional distribution systems** from the equation and keep the energy network physically short. This reduces both costs and regulatory complications. The idea of including energy sharing in local planning is gaining traction, but it depends heavily on technical feasibility and partner proximity.

There is also **growing recognition of the importance of thermal efficiency** alongside renewable electricity. Implementing PV on poorly insulated buildings is seen as counterproductive, as it undermines overall energy performance. Integrated planning that considers both heat and electricity upgrades is therefore essential.

In terms of future development, one valuable lesson is the importance of anticipating investor behaviour. **Local authorities have begun exploring how to encourage or require renewable energy investments from companies purchasing land in industrial zones.** This includes evaluating their interest in participating in energy sharing schemes or integrating existing renewable energy sources. Such mechanisms could become key tools for promoting local energy autonomy.

Battery storage is emerging as a strategic enabler of local energy resilience. Stakeholders advocate for installing batteries at each transformer station, allowing surplus PV electricity to be stored before it enters the grid. This would support system stability and create more flexible, decentralised energy management. Finally, **practical infrastructure planning remains central.** There are plans to extend both the district heating pipelines and the electrical grid, suggesting that physical infrastructure is still a critical component of enabling long-term energy cooperation.

These lessons underscore the need for strategic, integrated planning, aligned with both economic realities and evolving policy frameworks. They also highlight the importance of flexibility and innovation in designing energy solutions that are both practical and scalable at the local level.

3.4.4 Skill gaps and training formats

3.4.4.1 *Results from interviews*

Interviewees have highlighted a number of skills gaps and training needs that hinder more effective implementation and cooperation. Several forms of capacity building have already been tested or suggested, with varying degrees of success.

One of the key challenges is a lack of experience, particularly in how local energy initiatives affect institutional structures like accounting. This gap underscores the need for tailored, practical learning opportunities that go beyond general knowledge.

In terms of training formats, stakeholders expressed a preference for coaching, training sessions, and workshops that are **specific to their context.** Importantly, study visits to other organisations and peer-to-peer learning were seen as highly valuable. These formats allow participants to see concrete examples of implementation and engage in direct exchanges about challenges and solutions.

While online seminars are appreciated for their convenience, and site visits offer practical inspiration, thematic workshops were often seen as too abstract or general. There is a clear concern that what works in one place might not be directly transferable to another, and participants are looking for training that is grounded in their local reality.

Participants also noted that the early list of topics currently proposed for training by ENERGIZE do not meet their needs—indicating a disconnect between what is being offered and what is actually useful on the ground. One area where there is demand, however, is **legal training**, particularly concerning the regulatory and legislative framework for renewable energy and energy cooperation. This suggests that improved understanding of legal constraints and opportunities could help stakeholders navigate their projects more confidently.

Overall, the message is clear: for training and upskilling to be effective, it must be **locally relevant, practical, and legally informed, with an emphasis on peer learning and context-specific support** rather than generic solutions.

3.4.4.2 *Results from survey*

Respondents generally show a **strong baseline understanding of energy topics**: 48% report having good knowledge, while 39% are familiar with the main concepts. Reflecting this interest, **70% attended a training on renewable energy in 2024**. The topics covered were diverse, ranging from energy communities (including subsidies, functioning, legal frameworks, and establishment), energy sharing, and battery storage, to the role of active customers and energy companies, ESG principles, training for energy specialists, methods to assess PV plant efficiency, and the technical requirements for installing flow meters.

Looking ahead, training on **local renewable energy production technologies** is in high demand. The most requested topic is **energy storage** (86%), followed by combined heat and power (45%), solar technologies (41%), renewable energy fundamentals (36%), district heating (32%), and wind energy (27%).

In relation to **energy communities**, respondents are particularly interested in **technologies that support their implementation**—such as software and equipment (61%)—as well as **business models** (57%), the functioning of energy production and sharing mechanisms (52%), and success stories from existing communities (52%). Organisational models are also considered important by 43%.

Training on financing mechanisms is another key area of interest. **Regional funding opportunities are the most requested topic (80%), followed by EU structural and investment plans (60%)**. On the policy side, training on **EU and national legislation regarding renewable energy and energy communities** is in high demand, with 74% and 58% of respondents prioritising these themes, respectively.

Regarding preferred training formats, **70% of respondents favour webinars**, highlighting a preference for accessible and time-efficient learning. Self-paced online courses are the second most popular (43%), while 35% of respondents would value thematic in-person workshops and study visits.

3.4.5 **User personas and user experience maps**

Based on the data collected in the Zlín region, two key user personas emerge that illustrate the current dynamics around energy cooperation and community-driven initiatives.

The first is the **“Interested but sceptical” persona**—typically a representative of a large enterprise or local manufacturing company. This persona is aware of rising energy costs and shows genuine interest in innovative energy solutions, including local energy communities. However, they remain cautious, citing uncertainty around regulatory frameworks, long payback periods, and the complexity of multi-actor coordination. Their mindset is shaped by pragmatism and optimisation: they are open to collaboration but require concrete guarantees of economic benefit, technical reliability, and minimal administrative burden.

The second is the **“Committed civil servant”**—a representative of municipal government, a regional agency, or an innovation-focused public body. This profile views energy communities as a strategic tool for local resilience, regional development, and public-private collaboration. They are motivated by the potential to strengthen local economies, retain talent, and creating synergies between urban and peri-

urban areas. However, they often face challenges in engaging local businesses, navigating political expectations, and translating long-term visions into actionable steps. They seek practical models of governance, legal clarity, and support in building trusted relationships with industry actors.

This duality reflects a broader opportunity in Zlín’s path toward energy transition: leveraging the region’s industrial roots and strong public infrastructure to build new forms of cooperation. Understanding the perspectives, barriers, and drivers of both personas will be essential to shaping inclusive engagement strategies and capacity-building efforts that resonate with the realities of a semi-industrialised, forward-looking territory.

Figure 17 "Interested but sceptical" persona card for Czech pilot

Figure 18 "Committed civil servant" persona card Czech pilot

Experience map "Interested but sceptical" persona Zlín Region

STAGE	1. AWARENESS <small>(THEY REALISE THEY HAVE A PROBLEM TO SOLVE)</small>	2. CONSIDERATION <small>(THEY TRY TO FIGURE OUT IF ENERGIZE IS A GOOD SOLUTION)</small>	3. SIGN-UP <small>(THEY ENROLL IN OUR PLATFORM AND TRAININGS)</small>	4. USE <small>(THEY CARRY OUT THE TRAININGS, ONLINE AND F2F)</small>	5. ADVOCACY <small>(THEY ADVOCATE AND RECOMMEND ENERGIZE)</small>
GOALS What do they want to achieve? Why?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce energy costs Add value reducing costs (waste, transport, resources, time) Optimise waste Connect with local companies re: energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pick up most effective learning opportunity Access examples of good practices 	<p>Go through a smooth and fast process</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start using the trainings ASAP Use the new knowledge at work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Persuade head of factory to invest in energy cooperation Convert neighbour enterprises to the idea of REC
ACTIONS What steps do they take?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ask local business/industry organisations Search on the web Find regional energy agency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Check our website Search for testimonials Read through training packages on offer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share internally Set-up an account Sign-up for specific trainings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Go through content Engage with fellow learners Utilise FAQ or chatbot for support Invite other relevant employees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommend to other companies Receives a completion certificate Receives feedback from his team Provides a testimonial on his experience
TOUCHPOINTS What/who are they interacting with?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local business/industry organisation Local events Survey/interviews EAZK Energy agencies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ platform ENERGIZE+ website Contact email 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online platform Contact email 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online platform Contact email Live online or F2F events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online platform Contact email Other fellow learners Local energy organisations/agencies
PAIN POINTS What are their barriers or challenges?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Afraid of REC upfront costs Poor conditions of their building Little information available on renewables bureaucracy Not familiar with business and financial models Problems with the grid 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Just "another EU project" Lack of staff dedicated to energy Unsure we are a good time investment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> They don't feel represented because Zlín is different from other regions and the trainings are not adapted to the local characteristics Hard to get relevant information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Most of the materials are in English 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> By sharing their experience they could give away their competitive advantage
OPPORTUNITIES What could be improved? What can we do for them at this stage? Which messages should we vehicle?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform them with possibilities Advocate for stronger national legislation and financing options for industrial energy cooperation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide clear outline of what they will learn Precise time commitment expected Frame ENERGIZE+ as a means to meet other businesses and discover existing initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure content is locally relevant 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allow them to share problems they are facing with other stakeholders Give feedback on their ideas/questions Be aware of other initiatives Provide tools to start a community Provide training in Czech 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support public recognition of the company as innovation leader and help boost CSR Put under the spotlight more users so that there can be a local community of "experts"

Figure 19 "Interested but sceptical" persona experience map (Zlín Region)

Experience map "Committed public servant" persona Zlín Region

STAGE	1. AWARENESS <small>(THEY REALISE THEY HAVE A PROBLEM TO SOLVE)</small>	2. CONSIDERATION <small>(THEY TRY TO FIGURE OUT IF ENERGIZE IS A GOOD SOLUTION)</small>	3. SIGN-UP <small>(THEY ENROLL IN OUR PLATFORM AND TRAININGS)</small>	4. USE <small>(THEY CARRY OUT THE TRAININGS, ONLINE AND F2F)</small>	5. ADVOCACY <small>(THEY ADVOCATE AND RECOMMEND ENERGIZE)</small>
GOALS What do they want to achieve? Why?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create incentives for enterprises to adopt renewables Foster the economic of the local industrial park Create synergies between city and park 	<p>Understand if ENERGIZE+ programme is a time-effective resource and whether it can provide concrete tools</p>	<p>Go through a smooth and fast process</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start using the training ASAP Get applicable insights 	<p>Upskill other people so she doesn't have to carry all the burden</p>
ACTIONS What steps do they take?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Search on the Web Study national and regional laws Attend local events and taste the waters with local industry Send out newsletter/emails/surveys 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Check our website Search for testimonials Read through packages on offer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share internally Set up an account Sign up for specific trainings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invite relevant employees/colleagues Engage with fellow learners Go through content Utilise FAQ or chatbot for support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommend to other municipalities Receives a completion certificate Receives feedback from members Provides a testimonial on her experience
TOUCHPOINTS What/who are they interacting with?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local business/industry organisation Local events Survey/interviews EAZK Energy agencies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ website ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email Live online events Live F2F events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email
PAIN POINTS What are their barriers or challenges?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Since the framework is uncertain she feels she's constantly trying to catch up Companies are suspicious since there are no immediate benefits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unsure ENERGIZE+ programme is a good investment of time Doubts the programme has enough elements about the Czech context 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The first impression of the content does not meet her expectations (too little, too complicated, too simple...) Technical glitches on the platform The platform is confusing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty to follow the training if is delivered in English Content not adapted to her specific needs, too focused on industry Who will provide support at the end of the project? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Playing the role of the ambassador is time consuming and has no material reward Unsure whether the programme will be available long-term
OPPORTUNITIES What could be improved? What can we do for them at this stage? Which messages should we vehicle?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Present ENERGIZE+ Acceleration Programme as a structured opportunity to learn how incentivise and frame energy cooperation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide a clear outline of what they will learn, benefits and testimonials Precise the time commitment expected from their side Highlight the presence of Czech partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rigorous testing of the platform before the release Incorporate feedback from user research the training contents Test UX with beta testers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide subtitles/translation Set up a responsive customer care service (email, chatbot, FAQ) Structure the programme with holistic approach leaving space for new/improved content towards the end 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reflect on long-term sustainability: who is going to take over the platform? Elaborate a reward for advocates of the programme (visibility, direct access to key contacts/tools...)

Figure 20 "Committed public servant" persona experience map (Zlín region)

3.4.6 Conclusions for the Czech Pilot

Insights gathered through interviews and survey responses consistently highlight that **economic motivations are the primary driver** behind the energy transition in the Zlín region and neighbouring areas. Stakeholders frequently express this economic imperative in terms of a need to **reduce operational costs, increase self-sufficiency, and improve overall energy efficiency**. Cost savings also emerged as the **main incentive for joining or establishing energy communities**, particularly among municipalities and small- to medium-sized enterprises.

However, several significant **structural and regulatory barriers** continue to impede progress. A major concern is the **poor state of existing building stock**, particularly **rooftops**, which are often unsuitable for photovoltaic installations without substantial renovation. Similarly, the **urban infrastructure is not adequately prepared for district heating**. In both cases, stakeholders note that **available public incentives do not sufficiently cover the cost of required upgrades**, making these investments financially unattractive.

The **monopolistic structure of energy distribution**, combined with the **uncertainty of the legal and regulatory framework**, further complicates the situation. Stakeholders emphasise that the current conditions **discourage feeding electricity into the grid**, and instead make a strong case for **last-mile solutions**—such as **on-site production and self-consumption**. In this context, **battery storage is increasingly seen as a strategic asset**, both at the individual and community levels.

Among the challenges reported, the **complexity of the administrative and legal framework** stands out as the **most significant barrier**, closely followed by **uncertainty around return on investment (ROI)**. Many stakeholders report difficulties in navigating evolving legislation, particularly around grid access, community energy models, and support schemes.

Importantly, stakeholders caution against a **narrow focus on photovoltaic (PV) energy** alone. While PV is acknowledged as central to the transition, they stress the **equally critical role of thermal energy efficiency and district heating**, especially in the context of older buildings and dense urban settlements.

Some **local public authorities are exploring innovative strategies** to drive investment in renewable energy—such as **linking the purchase of land in industrial zones to commitments for clean energy deployment**. This indicates a willingness to experiment with regulatory tools to stimulate change, although concrete examples remain limited.

With regard to capacity building, stakeholders express a preference for **training opportunities that are practical, locally relevant, and legally informed**. Whether delivered online or face-to-face, such initiatives should prioritise **peer learning and hands-on support**, tailored to specific regional and legal contexts. Despite the challenges, it is worth noting that many stakeholders—particularly among local authorities and businesses—already demonstrate a **solid baseline knowledge of energy systems**, and show a **high level of interest in self-consumption strategies**, whether through batteries, smart load management, or collectively organised communities.

3.5 Upper Austria (Austria)

Upper Austria features diverse landscapes, including mountainous regions, plateaus, and river valleys. The Mühlviertel in the north is a granite plateau with poor soil, extensive woodlands, and grasslands. The central region is shaped by the Danube Valley, an important waterway. The southern region is dominated by the Alps, covering 62% of the state, with highlights like the Salzkammergut resort area, Kalkalpen National Park, and Hoher Dachstein (2,995 m) as the highest peak.

3.5.1 Energy context and regulation

Upper Austria is making significant progress in developing energy communities. The region is actively promoting renewable energy and energy efficiency initiatives, also with a focus on industrial areas (*Energy Leaders*, n.d.). As of December 2023, Upper Austria had established over 170 Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) with more than 3,000 members (Over 170 Renewable Energy Communities in Upper Austria - European Commission, n.d.). While not all of these are specifically in industrial parks, this demonstrates the region's commitment to energy communities. Furthermore, Upper Austria's regional energy agency has established a One-Stop Shop for Energy Communities. This service provides: Support to municipalities, households, and SMEs on regulatory, technical, financial, and organizational aspects of Energy Communities (“Over 170 Renewable Energy Communities in Upper Austria,” n.d.)

Given the limited data on energy communities in industrial parks, there is still significant need for further research and practical exploration. While some initiatives (see below) have emerged in Upper Austria, their impact so far remains modest and primarily exploratory. In Upper Austria, industrial cooperation is shaped by a well-established regional governance model. The INKOBA framework, short for Intercommunal Business Development Initiative, brings together municipalities in coordinated business development zones. There are currently 29 such INKOBAs across the region, each fostering joint spatial planning and economic infrastructure. Business Upper Austria, the province's business location agency, serves as the main coordinator of INKOBA activity. However, when it comes to topics like energy communities and sustainability, Business Upper Austria acts more as a facilitator or point of contact, directing inquiries to the Energy Agency of Upper Austria, which holds primary responsibility for such topics and includes the Cleantech Cluster Energy.

The INKOBA Sterngartl business park, for example, encompasses 12 municipalities and 12 established companies, representing a successful case of energy cooperation. In 2024, the business park joined the **Stern EEG**, a large-scale regional renewable energy community that includes over 800 members and a diversified energy portfolio: more than 600 PV systems, 11 hydroelectric plants, and 3 wind turbines. This decision was made after evaluating two options, and all but one large company in the park joined the cooperative.

Additionally, the Ennshafen industrial business park and port, located on the Danube at the border between Upper and Lower Austria, accommodates around 60 companies and over 2,300 employees. Integrated into the Rhine–Main–Danube Canal system, it offers continuous inland waterway transport from the Black Sea to the Atlantic Ocean. The site is managed by two public-private partnerships—Ennshafen OÖ GmbH and Ennshafen NÖ GmbH—responsible for operations and promotion. A wide range of industries are present at Ennshafen, including wood processing, recycling, logistics, industrial services, and manufacturing, alongside Austria's largest container terminal. The companies operate in diverse sectors and are mostly independent of each other, which contributes to a stable business environment. Given its structural characteristics and company mix, Ennshafen provides a potential setting for exploring the applicability of Eco-Industrial Park principles in practice (Rodin & Moser, 2022).

3.5.2 Energy transition and energy cooperation efforts in Upper Austria

Energy communities in Upper Austria face a range of significant and interconnected challenges that hinder their development and widespread implementation. One of the primary barriers lies in the legal and organisational complexity involved in establishing such communities. Energy communities must adopt specific legal forms, yet there remains considerable uncertainty about which structures are most appropriate—particularly in relation to taxation. This ambiguity can deter interested stakeholders from taking the first step.

Another substantial limitation is the restriction on who can participate in energy communities. Large companies are currently excluded from participating or holding decision-making authority in these initiatives, which significantly curtails their potential for growth, innovation, and financial investment. This regulatory constraint limits the appeal and viability of industrial-scale collaborations within the renewable energy sector.

Ownership rights further complicate the picture. In many cases, energy communities are required to hold ownership over generation assets, such as photovoltaic systems. However, this is often not feasible when private prosumers—especially those with rooftop PV installations—retain ownership themselves. This disconnect between legal requirements and practical realities poses a barrier to expanding energy-sharing models.

On the technical side, limitations related to grid infrastructure also present a challenge. Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) are legally restricted to operating within the grid area of a single Distribution System Operator (DSO). In regions where multiple DSOs operate, this stipulation can be a serious obstacle to cross-community cooperation and integration of renewable sources.

Financial and economic hurdles compound these difficulties. Establishing an energy community requires initial investment and access to seed capital to develop the necessary infrastructure. The recent energy crisis has also disrupted the economic logic behind energy communities. As market prices fluctuate, producers often find it more profitable to sell electricity on the open market or via existing support schemes, rather than through community-based models. In some cases, existing communities are even losing members, as electricity producers opt to sell to the green electricity clearing agent, drawn by higher feed-in tariffs.

Stakeholder engagement and public awareness are also pressing issues. Identifying and mobilising interested participants remains difficult, as many potential members lack either the interest or understanding required to actively engage in such initiatives. There is a clear need for broader education and communication strategies to enhance public acceptance and familiarity with the benefits of energy communities. Furthermore, the administrative burden associated with founding and running these communities is often perceived as overwhelming. The extensive documentation, regulatory compliance, and organisational work involved can discourage both individuals and businesses from pursuing this path.

Altogether, these challenges reveal that while the concept of energy communities is promising, significant legal, financial, technical, and social barriers must be addressed to unlock their full potential in Upper Austria.

3.5.3 Stakeholder mapping

The actors identified in Upper Austria for co-creation can be grouped in the following categories:

- Industrial parks and business associations
- Individual industries in industrial parks (chemicals, manufacturing, logistics)
- Public administration (municipalities)

- Energy businesses (operators, distributors, utilities, consultancies)

Stakeholders Map Upper Austria (update)

Figure 21 Stakeholder map (Upper Austria)

Stakeholder	Type	Relevance
Municipality Leonfelden	Bad Public administration	They will be involved as ambassadors and partners of the Acceleration Programme, which can support the reach of their energy targets.
Biz-UP	Development Agency	They will be involved in survey and interviews; later, they will be involved as beneficiaries of the Acceleration Programme.
INKOBA Sterngartl Industrial Area Ennschafen	Industrial Park	They will be involved as ambassadors and partners of the

		Acceleration Programme, which can support the reach of their energy targets.
Park Managers		They will be involved to...
Individual industries (chemicals, manufacturing, logistics)	Industry	They will be involved in survey and interviews; later, they will be involved as beneficiaries of the Acceleration Programme

Table 4 Stakeholder mapping Upper Austria

3.5.4 Survey respondents' profile

Survey participation for Upper Austria was very low. Despite several respondent recruitment and outreach attempts, only 6 responses were collected, of which 4 were fully completed and 2 partially completed. Despite repeated outreach efforts and various recruitment attempts, only six responses were collected in total, with four respondents completing the survey in full and two providing partial responses. This limited dataset significantly constrained the depth of analysis and made it impossible to develop meaningful respondent profiles or draw robust quantitative conclusions.

Nevertheless, the responses that were received do offer some indicative insights and recurring themes that align with findings from the expert interviews. While not statistically representative, they provide anecdotal support for certain qualitative observations, such as the perceived importance of financial incentives, the preference for practical over theoretical information, and the limited internal capacity within some organisations to engage with energy cooperation initiatives.

Given these constraints, the survey results are presented here in an illustrative rather than conclusive manner. They should be interpreted with caution and seen as supplementary to the more extensive findings gathered through interviews and desk research. These challenges also highlight the need for more targeted engagement strategies and simplified survey formats in future research involving businesses and industrial park stakeholders.

3.5.5 Priorities and motivations for the energy transition

3.5.5.1 *Results from interviews*

The interviews highlighted several key priorities and motivations driving the energy transition within industrial parks and among associated stakeholders in Upper Austria.

Foremost among these is the desire to reduce energy costs. Economic considerations are a primary motivator for companies, particularly in the face of rising energy prices and increasing regulatory pressure. Energy cooperation is seen as a strategic means to enhance efficiency and reduce long-term operational expenses.

Climate change and related policy developments also play a significant role. Companies are increasingly aware that environmental regulations will impact their operations, and some are motivated by a broader commitment to sustainability. However, this motivation is often secondary to financial and compliance-related concerns.

Another key driver is the opportunity to future-proof business operations. By participating in collective energy initiatives or adopting renewable technologies, companies hope to improve their resilience and adaptability in a rapidly changing energy landscape.

Networking and collaboration were also cited as indirect but valuable motivations. Participation in workshops or energy-related initiatives provides companies with opportunities to connect with other local businesses, share knowledge, and build partnerships.

Finally, local and regional authorities—such as INKOBA managers and the Upper Austrian business agency—are motivated by goals of strategic area development, efficient use of shared infrastructure, and enhancing the economic attractiveness of their regions. For them, the energy transition is linked to long-term competitiveness and sustainable regional planning.

3.5.5.2 *Results from survey*

The survey responses, though limited in sample size (6–7 respondents per question), suggest several trends in organisational priorities. Cost reduction emerged as the most frequently cited goal (33%, 2 out of 6 respondents), aligning with economic pressures facing industrial sectors. However, half of respondents (50%, 3 out of 6) selected "Other" for energy goals, indicating unlisted motivations may dominate. Notably, only 17% (1 out of 6) prioritised environmental sustainability or renewable adoption, contrasting with typical energy transition narratives.

Energy sourcing data revealed heavy reliance on grid electricity (average 56% of energy mix) and gas (40%), with renewables playing a minor role (20%). This dependency may explain why 83% (5 out of 6) rejected joining energy communities—a stark divergence from earlier surveys. The dominance of large companies (50% of respondents) and leadership roles (50% CEOs, 33% energy managers) in responses suggests decision-makers prioritise operational continuity over experimental cooperation models.

3.5.6 Barriers for energy cooperation

3.5.6.1 *Results from interviews*

Several barriers currently hinder the broader development of industrial energy communities in Upper Austria. One of the primary challenges is the absence of any legal obligation for companies to participate. Engagement in energy cooperation remains entirely voluntary, and business park managers lack the authority to compel companies to take part. This voluntary nature is further complicated by a prevailing individualistic mindset among many firms. Businesses often regard themselves as independent entities with little incentive to act collectively or perceive themselves as part of a wider community.

Another significant barrier is the limited internal capacity within companies to address energy cooperation. In many cases, there is no dedicated energy manager, or the person responsible lacks either the interest or the mandate to pursue additional collaborative initiatives. This lack of internal drive can severely limit the ability to move from discussion to implementation.

Time also presents a major constraint. Establishing relationships and maintaining open communication with companies requires a considerable investment of time, particularly in the initial phases. Building trust and convincing firms to explore energy cooperation involves persistent and often personalised engagement, which can be difficult to sustain without dedicated resources.

Furthermore, current regulations exclude some larger companies from joining renewable energy communities, creating structural barriers to full participation. This restriction limits the potential scope and impact of energy communities, particularly in business parks with a high concentration of large industrial players.

Lastly, there is a degree of resistance to engaging in purely theoretical conversations about sustainability. Many companies show little interest in abstract discussions and are more likely to engage when there are clear, practical benefits. As such, initiatives must prioritise demonstrating tangible outcomes and economic value to secure broader buy-in from the private sector.

3.5.6.2 *Results from survey*

Respondents identified multiple obstacles to energy collaboration, with upfront costs being most prominent (33%, 2 out of 6). Administrative complexity and regulatory hurdles each concerned 17% (1 out of 6), while mismatched goals and cybersecurity worries showed equal prevalence. The 33% (2 out of 6) selecting "Other" barriers implies significant unaddressed challenges.

Notably, 83% (5 out of 6) declined energy community participation, contrasting sharply with their 100% adoption of anonymised data use (Q1). This paradox may reflect distrust in shared-energy models despite accepting research collaboration. The absence of concerns about technical reliability (0%) suggests non-technical barriers—financial, bureaucratic, or cultural—are primary impediments.

3.5.7 **Lessons learned from local energy cooperation initiatives**

3.5.7.1 *Results from interviews*

The interviews revealed several important lessons learned from local energy cooperation initiatives in Upper Austria, offering valuable insight into what facilitates or hinders progress.

One of the most prominent lessons is the importance of early and proactive engagement. Energy cooperation is more likely to succeed when discussions around sustainability and shared energy use begin during the site selection or business settlement phase. This allows expectations to be clearly communicated and aligned from the outset, making collaboration more natural and integrated into business operations.

Trust-building and personal engagement were also identified as essential. Face-to-face interactions, especially in the initial phases, help to build rapport and establish a foundation for cooperation. Matchmaking efforts and individual consultations were particularly effective in encouraging participation and addressing doubts or uncertainties.

Another key lesson is that external facilitation can be critical. Neutral mediators—such as regional agencies or energy experts—play a vital role in initiating dialogue, translating technical details into concrete benefits, and maintaining momentum. Without such support, companies often lack the capacity or incentive to explore cooperative models on their own.

The experience also highlighted that companies respond best to practical and tangible outcomes. Abstract sustainability goals or lengthy theoretical discussions tend to generate little interest. Demonstrating economic and operational benefits, providing planning tools, and offering clear pathways to implementation are far more effective in securing engagement.

Moreover, the presence of motivated individuals, such as energy managers or engaged municipal leaders, can significantly influence success. Where such champions exist, initiatives tend to move forward more quickly and with greater buy-in.

Finally, regulatory clarity and inclusion remain crucial. Legal ambiguities and participation restrictions—particularly for larger companies—can stall or limit energy cooperation. Clarifying these frameworks and making energy communities more accessible to all business sizes will be key to expanding successful models in the future.

3.5.7.2 *Results from survey*

With only 17% (1 out of 6) willing to join energy communities and 33% (2 out of 6) attending related events, engagement levels were low. Yet, existing adopters showed specific interests:

- **Technology:** Current adopters use solar PV (50%, 3 out of 6) and EV charging (50%), while planned investments focus on heat pumps (20%, 1 out of 5) and district heating (20%).
- **Financing:** Heavy reliance on own funds (80%, 4 out of 5) suggests distrust in external financing mechanisms.
- **Policy:** The sole policy training request (Q23) was for energy efficiency regulation, ignoring renewables—a possible misalignment with EU priorities.

These patterns indicate that successful initiatives must address financial independence and demonstrate proven technologies rather than theoretical benefits.

3.5.8 Skill gaps and training formats

3.5.8.1 *Results from interviews*

The interviews highlighted several skill gaps and training needs that are currently limiting the broader uptake of industrial energy cooperation initiatives in Upper Austria.

A key gap lies in the technical and regulatory understanding required to develop and manage renewable energy communities. Many business park managers and municipal leaders are not energy experts, and companies often lack staff with the specific knowledge needed to evaluate or implement collective energy solutions. In particular, understanding **the legal frameworks, financing models, and technical planning** for energy communities remains a challenge.

There is also a need for capacity building in **strategic communication and facilitation**. Skills related to stakeholder engagement, trust-building, and coordination are essential for driving collaboration among diverse actors, especially in settings where participation is voluntary and driven by mutual benefit rather than obligation.

To address these gaps, a variety of training formats have been employed or proposed. Interviewees emphasized that no single format works best for all stakeholders. On-site meetings and workshops are particularly valued for their opportunities for direct exchange, personal interaction, and building relationships. These formats help translate abstract concepts into concrete discussions and foster a sense of shared purpose.

Webinars and online seminars are considered useful, but only when they are short, focused, and designed to deliver practical insights. Lengthy or overly theoretical sessions tend to lose participant interest. A blended approach—combining short online inputs with in-person follow-ups—was suggested as an effective model for ongoing knowledge transfer.

Internal and external training events have proven beneficial, not only for deepening subject knowledge but also for fostering a culture of continuous learning within organisations like Business Upper Austria. Structured exchanges between INKOBAs, peer learning from successful examples, and technical

workshops supported by the Energy Agency or other neutral facilitators were all seen as valuable components of a broader capacity-building strategy.

3.5.8.2 *Results from survey*

The minimal response to training questions (1–2 respondents) limits conclusions but reveals tentative preferences:

- Topics: Energy storage was the sole requested technical topic (100%, 1 out of 1), while organisational models and business frameworks drew equal interest in community-related training (50% each, 1 out of 2).
- Formats: Live webinars were universally preferred (100%, 2 out of 2), with workshops at 50% (1 out of 2). Notably, no respondents chose self-paced learning or study visits.

This suggests professionals prioritise interactive, expert-led sessions over self-directed or experiential learning. The absence of interest in EU funding programmes (0%) contrasts with policy expectations, potentially indicating local/regional solutions are favoured over complex transnational schemes.

3.5.9 User personas and user experience maps

Based on the findings from Upper Austria, two key user personas emerge that reflect current attitudes and constraints around industrial energy cooperation and the broader energy transition.

The first is the **Pragmatic Cost-Cutter**, represented by Lena, a small business owner or operations manager in a manufacturing or processing company. Lena operates within a tight financial and human resource envelope, often juggling several responsibilities with little specialised staff. Her interest in energy issues is driven primarily by the need to cut costs and maintain profitability in a volatile market environment. Rising energy prices have pushed her to consider energy-saving measures and occasionally explore renewable options, but action is only taken when it promises a short return on investment and low disruption. While there is a growing awareness that regulations will become stricter, the main concern remains compliance, not innovation. Lena is sceptical of energy communities, viewing them as administratively complex and strategically risky—especially if it means giving up control over energy decisions. For her, voluntary collaboration must be backed by a clear economic rationale and minimal additional workload. Trust in external coordination is low, and self-reliance is valued over shared models. She is not opposed to sustainability in principle, but it must be framed in terms of operational continuity, risk reduction, and long-term cost optimisation.

The second persona is the **Isolated Environmental Advocate**, represented by Markus, an environmentally conscious energy officer or manager working within a larger industrial firm. Markus is personally committed to the energy transition and is often one of the few voices within his organisation advocating for renewable energy, carbon reduction, or community-based solutions. His motivation stems from a strong sense of environmental responsibility and alignment with EU or national climate goals. However, he often finds himself in an uphill battle to secure internal buy-in. While technically informed and enthusiastic, his proposals are frequently met with indifference or resistance from senior leadership, who are primarily concerned with cost and operational risk. Markus is eager to participate in energy communities and sees value in collaborative models, but struggles to move beyond pilot-stage initiatives due to a lack of organisational mandate or decision-making power. He attends workshops, builds informal networks, and seeks external support, but his efforts are often isolated and insufficient to drive systemic change. The result is a kind of professional isolation: a motivated change agent without the institutional backing to implement wider reforms. For this persona, capacity-building efforts must offer not only

technical tools but also strategies for internal advocacy, cross-departmental engagement, and long-term organisational alignment.

These two personas capture the spectrum of current dynamics in Upper Austria’s industrial energy landscape—from financially-driven caution to values-based innovation. Engaging both profiles effectively will require tailored strategies: pragmatic framing and low-threshold offers for Lena, and empowerment and institutional support for Markus.

Figure 22 “Pragmatic Cost Cutter” Persona card

Figure 23 “Isolated Environmental Advocate” persona card

Experience map "Pragmatic Cost-Cutter" persona Upper Austria

STAGE	1. AWARENESS <small>(THEY REALISE THEY HAVE A PROBLEM TO SOLVE)</small>	2. CONSIDERATION <small>(THEY TRY TO FIGURE OUT IF ENERGIZE IS A GOOD SOLUTION)</small>	3. SIGN-UP <small>(THEY ENROLL IN OUR PLATFORM AND TRAININGS)</small>	4. USE <small>(THEY CARRY OUT THE TRAININGS, ONLINE AND F2F)</small>	5. ADVOCACY <small>(THEY ADVOCATE AND RECOMMEND ENERGIZE)</small>
GOALS What do they want to achieve? Why?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce energy costs Understand if joining a REC is a good deal for the company 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pick up most effective learning opportunity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Go through a smooth and fast process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start using the training ASAP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Convert neighbour enterprises to the idea of the REC
ACTIONS What steps do they take?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Search on the Web Ask local business/industry organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Check our website Search for testimonials Read through packages on offer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share internally Set up an account Sign up for specific trainings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share the account with relevant employees Engage with fellow learners Go through content Utilise FAQ or chatbot for support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommend to other companies Receives a completion certificate Receives feedback from her team Provides a testimonial on her experience
TOUCHPOINTS What/who are they interacting with?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local business/industry organisation Survey/interviews Local events EI-JKU 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ website ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email Live online events Live F2F events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email
PAIN POINTS What are their barriers or challenges?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Afraid of REC upfront costs Navigating renewables bureaucracy Doesn't trust the industry park manager 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unsure ENERGIZE+ programme is a good investment of time What is Energize? Who are the partners? Unsure where to start Trouble understanding English 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The first impression of the content does not meet her expectations (too little, too complicated, too simple...) Technical glitches on the platform The platform is confusing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty to follow the training if is delivered in English Who will provide support at the end of the project? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Didn't really use the platform Not really sure if Energize works No use of the certificate = No added value She doesn't know how to explain Energize
OPPORTUNITIES What could be improved? What can we do for them at this stage? Which messages should we vehicle?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Input for reporting CSRD Reducing CO2 Potential economic benefits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meet people/companies from other countries participating in the Energize pilots Precise the time commitment expected from their side Inform via email all the companies in industrial parks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rigorous testing of the platform before the release Incorporate feedback from user research the training contents Test UX with beta testers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide subtitles/translation Set up a responsive customer care service (email, chatbot, FAQ) Structure the programme leaving space for new/improved content towards the end 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New skills

Figure 24 - "Pragmatic Cost-Cutter" persona experience journey map (Upper Austria region)

Experience map "Isolated Environmental Advocate" persona Upper Austria

STAGE	1. AWARENESS <small>(THEY REALISE THEY HAVE A PROBLEM TO SOLVE)</small>	2. CONSIDERATION <small>(THEY TRY TO FIGURE OUT IF ENERGIZE IS A GOOD SOLUTION)</small>	3. SIGN-UP <small>(THEY ENROLL IN OUR PLATFORM AND TRAININGS)</small>	4. USE <small>(THEY CARRY OUT THE TRAININGS, ONLINE AND F2F)</small>	5. ADVOCACY <small>(THEY ADVOCATE AND RECOMMEND ENERGIZE)</small>
GOALS What do they want to achieve? Why?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce energy costs Understand if joining a REC is a good deal for the company Help the company to become more sustainable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand if ENERGIZE+ programme is a time-effective resource and whether it can provide concrete tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Go through a smooth and fast process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start using the training and learn within own learning rhythm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Convert management to join an energy community Show the value of energy communities to get more resources from the company and train new team members
ACTIONS What steps do they take?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Search on the Web Ask local business/industry organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Check our website Search for testimonials Read through packages on offer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set up an account Sign up for specific trainings Share internally 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Take most relevant training sessions first Engage with fellow learners Go through content Utilise FAQ or chatbot for support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommend to other team members Receives feedback from his team and management Provides a testimonial on his experience
TOUCHPOINTS What/who are they interacting with?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local business/industry organisation Company management Survey/interviews Local events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ website ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email Live online events Live F2F events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENERGIZE+ learning platform Contact email
PAIN POINTS What are their barriers or challenges?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Internal decision-making is slow, especially for collaborative or "experimental" models Management prioritises cost and compliance over broader sustainability goals Lacks understanding of legal and financial frameworks for energy communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unsure ENERGIZE+ programme is a good investment of time Worries about how to present the value to management Time restrictions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information is not actionable enough to convince management Explanations are too broad Hard to find specific information (doesn't want to complete all training units) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty to follow the training if is delivered in English Who will provide support at the end of the project? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Content doesn't align with company goals and procedure Little reach outside the company as he has only mid-level decision making power
OPPORTUNITIES What could be improved? What can we do for them at this stage? Which messages should we vehicle?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Present ENERGIZE+ Acceleration Programme as a structured opportunity to acquire new resources and leverages for maintaining and expanding the community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide a clear outline of what they will learn, benefits and testimonials Precise the time commitment expected from their side Highlight benefits for companies of all sizes and provide actionable key messages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure a more focused learning is possible for users with little time Make content actionable and help users with pitching benefits of energy communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide subtitles/translation Set up a responsive customer care service (email, chatbot, FAQ) Structure the programme leaving space for new/improved content towards the end 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Make benefits for bigger companies clear (e.g. peer recognition, awards opportunity to be seen as industry leaders) Elaborate a reward for advocates of the programme (visibility, direct access to key advice/tools...)

Figure 25 "Isolated Environmental Advocate" persona experience map (Upper Austria region)

3.5.10 Conclusions for the Upper Austrian Pilot

The development of industrial energy cooperation in Upper Austria is marked by both cautious pragmatism and emerging potential. While the energy transition is clearly on the radar of companies, especially in light of rising energy prices and tightening regulations, action remains uneven and often limited to low-risk, economically justified measures. The motivation to engage in deeper forms of collaboration, such as renewable energy communities, is hindered by a mix of structural, regulatory, and cultural barriers.

Interviews and limited survey responses alike point to a dominant mindset shaped by cost-consciousness and operational control. Many businesses continue to view themselves as isolated actors, wary of complex, collective models and sceptical of the return on investment in sustainability initiatives. Yet, within this landscape, there are individuals—such as energy managers and municipal facilitators and experts from applied research—who are actively trying to drive change. Their experiences underscore the importance of early engagement, trusted facilitation, and a focus on tangible, practical outcomes.

Local authorities and support agencies have a key role to play in lowering the threshold for participation. This includes simplifying administrative processes, clarifying regulatory frameworks, and investing in targeted capacity-building. Sharing successful examples and enabling peer-to-peer learning can further help shift attitudes from cautious observation to confident experimentation.

Ultimately, the challenge in Upper Austria is not a lack of awareness, but a lack of alignment—between environmental goals and economic realities, between visionary individuals and institutional inertia. Bridging this gap will require coordinated efforts that respect local business logic while opening space for more inclusive and resilient energy solutions. The groundwork is there, but translating potential into practice will depend on sustained support, strategic communication, and policy frameworks that make cooperation not just possible, but preferable.

4 Comparative analysis

4.1 Priorities and motivations for the energy transition

Cost reduction as the primary motivation

Across all four regions, cost reduction stands out as the dominant motivation driving the energy transition. This focus on reducing operational expenses reflects the economic pressures that businesses face in the context of volatile energy prices and stringent regulatory frameworks. However, while the goal of reducing costs is shared, the approaches to achieving this vary depending on regional priorities and available technologies.

Environmental sustainability and climate goals

Environmental sustainability is consistently acknowledged as an important driver, though it is generally considered secondary to cost reduction. This is particularly true in the Zlín Region and Upper Austria, where financial considerations clearly outweigh environmental goals in driving the transition. In contrast, **Valsesia places a somewhat stronger emphasis on sustainability**, with respondents expressing a desire not only to adopt renewable energy but also to foster local cooperation and territorial development through energy communities (CERs). Catalonia also acknowledges the importance of sustainability, but the focus remains primarily on cost-saving initiatives, with environmental goals playing a complementary role.

Energy communities and cooperation

The concept of energy communities is gaining traction, but the level of interest in joining them varies. **Upper Austria shows a more cautious stance**, with relatively low interest in energy communities despite the economic incentives. This indicates that the benefits of collective action may not be well communicated or perceived as tangible enough, especially in financial terms. Similarly, the **Zlín Region** shows moderate interest in ECs, with economic motivations driving participation but also a sense of caution due to technical uncertainties and regulatory complexities.

In contrast, Italy and Catalonia demonstrate a stronger engagement with the idea of energy communities. In **Italy**, the CER model is seen not only as a way to reduce energy costs but also as **a means to foster local collaboration, territorial development, and shared responsibility**.

The emphasis on community building in Catalonia, particularly in **Manresa**, highlights the social aspect of energy transition, where **knowledge-sharing and local business networks** play a critical role in fostering collective action.

Technical installations priorities

Across the four pilots, **photovoltaic (PV)** systems are the most common planned installations, underlining the broad shift towards solar energy as a key part of energy autonomy. The **growing interest in electric vehicle (EV) charging stations** and **battery storage systems** in Catalonia and Zlín reflects an increasing recognition of the need for infrastructure that supports the broader adoption of renewable energy, enhancing energy security and flexibility. Valsesia also stands out for its interest in strengthening local **biomass value chains**, which would significantly localise energy production.

Strategic and long-term motivations

Long-term goals such as **energy autonomy, long-term cost savings, and operational resilience** resonate strongly with stakeholders across the regions. In Upper Austria, stakeholders are particularly focused on future-proofing operations, ensuring long-term competitiveness, and improving energy autonomy, which are seen as essential to adapting to an evolving energy landscape. In Italy, a similar desire for energy resilience is apparent, with stakeholders viewing renewables as a strategic choice to secure price stability and sustainable growth. Zlín also prioritises long-term energy resilience, with a focus on optimising self-

consumption and reducing reliance on the grid. In Catalonia, energy autonomy is closely linked with broader goals of sustainability, highlighting the intersection of economic and environmental motivations.

4.2 Perceived barriers and challenges

Administrative and regulatory complexity

Across all regions, administrative complexity is identified as a significant barrier to energy cooperation. In Catalonia, the complexity of administrative procedures, especially in regions without established lighthouse communities, deters participation. In Italy, restrictive legal frameworks and outdated infrastructure present major hurdles, with regulatory inefficiencies complicating compliance. Similarly, Upper Austria highlights administrative complexity as the leading barrier, while Zlín faces significant challenges due to bureaucratic inefficiencies at both local and national levels. These challenges are compounded by unclear or misaligned regulations that create uncertainty around compliance and implementation.

Financial constraints and high upfront costs

Financial concerns are a consistent theme across all regions, particularly regarding upfront costs and the uncertainty around return on investment (ROI). In Zlín, high upfront costs are a prominent obstacle, alongside concerns about ROI and the financial viability of solar and other renewable energy installations. In Upper Austria, financial limitations are similarly cited, with significant concerns about the costs and financial risks of energy cooperation. In Italy, financial barriers are reinforced by the lack of resources to manage complex administrative processes, and in Catalonia, high upfront costs are noted as a key deterrent.

Technical and infrastructure challenges

Technical issues are another shared concern across regions, especially in relation to the suitability of existing infrastructure. In Zlín, the poor condition of infrastructure, such as unsuitable rooftops for photovoltaic (PV) systems, and fragmented energy management systems make integrated solutions difficult. Similarly, Valsesia and Catalonia highlight the challenge of outdated infrastructure, which limits scalability and makes it harder to implement renewable energy solutions effectively. In Upper Austria, the absence of technical capacity and the restrictive nature of some energy systems—especially in industrial parks—pose significant barriers. The need for upgrades and more modern energy infrastructure is crucial to overcome these challenges and unlock the potential for renewable energy integration.

Coordination and organisational challenges

Coordination difficulties within energy communities are particularly pronounced concerns across the pilots. In Valsesia and Catalonia, aligning internal procedures, timelines, and priorities among diverse stakeholders is seen as a major obstacle to the smooth implementation of energy cooperation initiatives. Stakeholders point to lengthy decision-making processes and complex coordination as significant deterrents. In Upper Austria, voluntary participation in energy communities, combined with a lack of internal capacity, especially in terms of dedicated personnel and decision-making authority, limits collaborative efforts. Similarly, in Zlín, misaligned interests and the absence of sufficient autonomy for decision-making at the local level further hinder energy cooperation.

Cultural and social factors

Cultural resistance to collective action is noted as a barrier in Upper Austria and Catalonia, where the region's **individualistic business culture** makes it harder to foster cooperation. This reluctance to collaborate, coupled with the voluntary nature of participation, adds a layer of complexity in mobilising stakeholders for energy cooperation. In Italy, while there is a growing interest in energy communities, the **lack of a broader cultural shift towards shared environmental responsibility** limits the pace of transition. Catalonia and Zlín region also face cultural barriers in the form of **trust issues**—there is widespread scepticism about the willingness of energy distributors to collaborate and about government support for energy communities. In Zlín, the **absence of trust in decentralised energy models and the regulatory instability** around such initiatives make long-term cooperation difficult.

Geographic and operational constraints

Geographic challenges are particularly relevant in Valsesia, where remoteness of some areas makes access to technical expertise difficult and limits the feasibility of large-scale renewable energy initiatives. Similarly, in Zlín, the challenge of seasonal demand fluctuations and technical constraints in urban planning further complicates efforts. In Catalonia, infrastructure challenges, including the presence of asbestos in industrial facilities, pose practical obstacles to the installation of solar panels and other renewable energy technologies. These logistical constraints—whether related to geography or infrastructure—further limit the ability to implement effective energy solutions.

Resource and capacity constraints

The lack of human and financial resources is a critical challenge in all regions. In Valsesia, stakeholders consistently mention the lack of staff expertise and digital tools to manage complex energy community projects, highlighting the need for automation and streamlined procedures. Similarly, in Upper Austria, the absence of dedicated personnel and the lack of organisational mandates to pursue energy cooperation limit the ability to engage in meaningful energy community development. In Zlín, the lack of internal capacity and limited decision-making autonomy also hinder energy cooperation efforts.

4.3 Lessons learned from existing energy cooperation initiatives

Leadership and trust building

One of the most striking commonalities is the pivotal role of leadership and trust-building in enabling these initiatives to take root. In Manresa, **strong leadership** through a dedicated manager who has been working thirty years at the Bufalvent industry association proved essential in fostering trust and sustaining engagement, even in the face of challenges. Such trust also made acceptable that although financial gains are a main motivator, they are a future promise rather than a current reality. Similarly, in Italy, the **active involvement of municipalities** is seen as a booster for cooperation, grounding them in the common good. In the Czech Republic, stakeholders suggest that trust can be cultivated through **strategies aligned with economic reality**—e.g. the emphasis on photovoltaic systems designed for self-consumption rather than export to the grid. Upper Austria stakeholders highlighted the importance of **early engagement and personalised support in building trust**. Here, neutral facilitators play a key role in bridging technical and organisational gaps, while individual champions within companies or local governments often tipped the balance between stalled projects and active implementation. Furthermore, a lack of documented examples of successful initiatives highlighted the need for more structured knowledge sharing, while the success of current projects hinged on the availability of simple, accessible operational models and administrative processes.

Planning

Planning and coordination emerged as another area of convergence. In Italy, a **feasibility study** provided a shared factual basis upon which to build collective action, reinforcing both the legitimacy and practicality of the proposed initiatives. Manresa's experience further underlined the value of **balancing ambition with realistic, concrete planning**—especially when navigating initial setbacks. Zlín stakeholders suggested that effective **planning must be integrated**, addressing not only electricity generation but also thermal efficiency and building insulation: this holistic approach is key to ensuring long-term energy performance. Upper Austria stakeholders echoed this perspective, emphasising the need of **embedding cooperation into business park strategies from the outset**, before companies become locked into conventional energy models.

Economic viability and independence

Manresa managing team highlighted the importance in onboarding of **presenting precise economic figures and projections** to industry representatives. Italian stakeholders underscored the need for **transparency in how economic benefits are shared** within energy communities, suggesting that clearly

defined and well-communicated financial models are crucial for sustaining participation. In the Czech Republic, economic viability is more closely linked to the physical design of energy systems: **short, local networks** and on-site energy consumption reduce dependence on expensive infrastructure and regulatory hurdles. Battery storage, especially when deployed at transformer stations, is increasingly seen as a strategic tool to boost local resilience and decentralised management.

4.4 Training needs

Across the four pilots, stakeholders express a shared recognition of critical knowledge gaps that must be addressed through targeted training. However, the specific content priorities and preferred formats for capacity building vary in response to each region's context and maturity in the energy transition.

In **Catalonia**, stakeholders openly admit having limited knowledge, especially on the legal and technical aspects of energy systems. There is a strong appetite for learning more about the creation, management, and governance of energy communities, as well as a desire to draw inspiration from the experiences of successful, established initiatives. On the technical side, solar energy, the fundamentals of renewables, and battery storage attract the most interest, while a more in-depth understanding of EU and regional policies and funding opportunities is also seen as critical. Regarding format, stakeholders favour accessible and flexible options, with live webinars and self-paced online modules being the most in demand, followed by individual coaching and in-person thematic workshops.

In **Valsesia**, while a foundational awareness of energy cooperation exists—often built through past participation in events and trainings—stakeholders are eager to go beyond the basics. They are particularly interested in deepening their knowledge of organisational and business models, successful case studies, regulatory frameworks, and effective community engagement strategies. Technical training on solar and biomass energy production remains essential, alongside growing interest in battery storage and combined heat and power technologies. Italian stakeholders also seek guidance on innovative financing models, including crowdfunding and revolving funds, and clearer understanding of national policy impacts on local initiatives. Here too, flexible learning formats are preferred, with online webinars topping the list, often complemented by occasional in-person workshops and peer-learning study visits. A digital resource hub to support long-term, self-paced learning was also suggested as a valuable complement to live training.

The **Czech** experience similarly reveals both a solid baseline of interest and areas of knowledge deficit, particularly in practical, context-sensitive aspects of implementation. Stakeholders in the Zlín Region strongly prefer hands-on learning formats such as coaching, study visits, and peer exchanges over abstract or overly general training. There is considerable demand for support on energy storage, combined heat and power, and the development of local renewable energy sources. Legislative understanding, especially around energy communities, remains a pressing need, along with practical insights into business models and funding mechanisms. While webinars and online courses are popular for their flexibility, Czech stakeholders also emphasise the irreplaceable value of face-to-face learning, particularly through thematic workshops that allow direct interaction and problem-solving tailored to local realities.

In **Upper Austria**, the focus is equally split between hard and soft skills. Stakeholders identify skill gaps in technical, legal, and financial areas, but also highlight the importance of facilitation, communication, and coordination—especially crucial in voluntary collaborations built on trust. Capacity building here is seen as a cornerstone of effective energy cooperation, and training efforts are expected to cater to a wide range of roles and needs. As in the other regions, there is strong interest in energy storage, solar technologies, and regulatory knowledge, alongside energy community business models. Preferred formats favour a blended approach that combines concise online modules with rich, interactive in-person engagements such as study visits. Live webinars and self-paced resources are also well regarded for their convenience and long-term value.

Training needs overview

Figure 26 Training needs overview

4.5 Stakeholders and personas: actionable insights for future project activities

Across the four pilots, the stakeholder mapping presents many similarities, with representatives of industry companies, industry associations and municipalities as main targets for both capacity building and co-creation. Public administration, financial entities and energy sector actors are allies for co-creation, since they can help ground the Acceleration Programme in the local reality.

The personas were elaborated on the basis of the interviews and surveys to reflect different positions towards energy cooperation, ranging from extremely sceptic to highly motivated stakeholders.

The most insightful components of the user journey exercise were the identification of pain points and opportunities, as they offer critical foresight into potential barriers to engagement as well as leverage points to maximise participation in the ENERGIZE Acceleration Programme. These insights are essential for designing support mechanisms and communication strategies that foster the successful enrolment and retention of a wide range of stakeholders throughout the programme. A closer look at each phase of the journey reveals the following general key considerations:

Awareness. When stakeholders begin exploring the topic of energy transition and cooperation, they do so through the lens of their existing assumptions and biases. This initial phase is therefore crucial for setting the tone and building trust.

Insights: the ENERGIZE Acceleration Programme must be clearly positioned as a reliable, structured learning pathway—one that introduces key concepts, data, and case-based evidence capable of convincing even sceptical decision-makers of the value of energy cooperation. Messaging at this stage should be clear, motivational, and informative, highlighting both the strategic and practical benefits of participation.

Consideration. As stakeholders weigh the decision to enrol in the programme, doubts may emerge. They may question whether ENERGIZE is a worthwhile use of their limited time, or whether its content is relevant to their specific regional and organisational context. Some may carry a degree of scepticism towards EU-funded initiatives, perceiving them as overly bureaucratic or misaligned with local priorities.

Insights: to address these concerns, the programme must offer a clear and transparent value proposition. This includes outlining what participants will concretely gain, how much time they are expected to invest, and how the acquired knowledge can be applied in their work. Offering compelling key messages that stakeholders can share with internal decision-makers—along with visible involvement from trusted local partners—will help build credibility and trust. Providing a direct point of contact for questions or clarifications is also essential to reduce perceived risk.

Enrolment. The moment of registration can present unexpected friction. Stakeholders may experience a gap between their expectations and the actual content or user interface of the platform. If the platform's navigation is not intuitive, or if its content feels disconnected from users' needs, their willingness to continue engaging may diminish.

Insights: these challenges can be mitigated through thorough usability testing and continuous integration of insights from user research, ensuring that the interface is user-friendly and the training materials are well-aligned with stakeholder priorities and capacities.

Engagement and learning. Once enrolled, stakeholders will interact with the platform and attend both online and in-person learning activities. However, sustained engagement may falter if content is available only in English or presented in overly abstract terms.

Insights: to maintain motivation, materials must be made accessible and contextually relevant. Offering multilingual content (or at least subtitles and translated summaries), setting up a responsive support service (via email, chatbot, or an updated FAQ), and establishing a system for regular feedback and content updates are all measures that can significantly enhance user experience. Ensuring that learning resources remain flexible, modular, and grounded in real-life applications will further support active participation.

Advocacy and retention. In the final stage of the journey, participants should be encouraged to become advocates for the programme, sharing their experience with peers and contributing to its visibility and impact. However, this role may be perceived as an additional burden, especially if there is no tangible benefit attached or if there are doubts about the long-term availability of the platform. Some stakeholders may also hesitate to promote a tool that competitors could access, fearing a loss of competitive advantage.

Insights: these concerns can be addressed by developing an advocacy reward system, which could include increased visibility for the organisation, privileged access to tools or expert advice, and public recognition of their pioneering role in energy cooperation. Building a sense of prestige and community around participation will help transform initial engagement into long-term commitment.

5 Conclusions

The bottom-up research conducted for this deliverable has highlighted stakeholders' motivations, perceived barriers, knowledge and experience with energy transition and cooperation across the four pilots. While cost reduction remains the dominant driver of energy transition efforts, it is increasingly complemented by motivations around environmental sustainability, energy autonomy, and local collaboration. At the same time, systemic barriers—including administrative complexity, financial and technical constraints, and cultural resistance—continue to hinder the pace and scale of cooperation. Despite these challenges, successful experiences point to the pivotal role of leadership, trust, practical planning, and tailored support in fostering energy communities and promoting strategic energy resilience.

The findings reaffirm the importance of designing engagement and capacity-building efforts that are context-sensitive, practically useful, and grounded in the lived experiences and needs of stakeholders. Whether through webinars, digital libraries, coaching, or immersive site visits, the evolution of ENERGIZE capacity building offering lies in formats that blend technical precision with accessible, context-sensitive delivery.

The following learnings will be applied in the Acceleration Programme development:

Develop modular, flexible learning pathways: leverage and organise existing resources to design a training programme that offers both foundational and advanced content, structured into self-contained modules covering technical, regulatory, financial, and organisational dimensions of energy communities.

Customise regional learning tracks: Tailor the content and case studies to address region-specific challenges—for example:

- Catalonia: Legal basics, technical feasibility, battery storage, and successful cases.
- Italy: Business models, biomass integration, financing tools, and regulatory adaptation.
- Zlín: Infrastructure retrofitting, cost-benefit analysis, and digital energy management.
- Upper Austria: Internal coordination, early-stage facilitation, and voluntary cooperation strategies.

Ensure inclusive delivery formats: Combine live webinars, self-paced online modules, and targeted in-person workshops to accommodate the availabilities and learning pace of the greatest number.

Monitor training impact and adapt accordingly: Include feedback loops and simple evaluation tools to track the relevance and usefulness of the training. Use this data to adjust content, fill remaining gaps, and keep the programme aligned with evolving needs.

For what concerns stakeholder engagement, the main takeaways are:

Activate regional peer-learning networks: facilitate experience-sharing across regions by organising exchanges between more mature and emerging initiatives (e.g. between Manresa and Zlín).

Support the emergence of local champions: identify and empower trusted figures—such as energy managers, municipal leaders, or industrial association representatives—who can advocate for ENERGIZE and bridge knowledge gaps, build trust, and drive cooperation within their regions.

Coordinate at multiple levels: encourage alignment and dialogue between local actors and national policymakers to address regulatory obstacles, clarify procedures, and secure long-term commitment to decentralised energy models.

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6 Annex 1 – Interview questions

6.1 Questions for stakeholders not part of an energy community

Q0. Can you describe your organisation? (scope, activities...)

Q1. Can you describe any existing initiatives from your organisation concerning energy sustainability? (what, since when, installations, share of energy coming from renewables, are there active plans for the near future...)

Q2. What is (or would be) the motivation for your organisation to engage more with renewables?

Q3. Which are the main barriers for your organisation to engage with renewables?

Q4. To what extent are you aware of any plans in the area concerning renewables?

Q5. Which are the main challenges and problems that your organisation faces when implementing and developing energy planning?

Q6. How would you define your knowledge of energy communities? 1. Limited 2. Sufficient 3. Deep

Q7. What kind of support (financial, knowledge, technical...) would help you in expanding your transition to renewables by joining an energy community?

"Q8. (CAPACITY BUILDING) In which of the following areas in relation to the energy transition do you perceive a knowledge/skills need within your organisation?

Local renewable energy production technologies	Emissions from waste and water sectors
	Wind
	Solar
	Hydroelectric
	Geothermal
	Combined heat and power
	District heating
	Other:
Energy communities	Organisational models
	business models
	Related technology (equipment like PV or EV charging stations, or apps to manage energy and money flow)
	success stories
	regulation

Energy poverty	Concept, EU measures & Best Practices
Finance	European Funding programmes (Horizon Europe, LIFE, Urbact...)
	Innovative financing (EPC, crowdfunding, revolving funds, etc.)
	European Structural and Investment funds (ERDF, Cohesion funds, etc.)
	Other:
Policies and regulations	Energy generation
	Energy efficiency
	Other specific sector?
Communication and engagement	Communication strategies: messages, channels, tools

"Q9. (CAPACITY BUILDING) Have you attended any capacity-building activity in the past 5 years? Yes/no
If yes: is there a format that you found particularly engaging or effective and that you want to recommend to us?"

"Q10. (CAPACITY BUILDING) What would be the best way for you to conduct training on energy cooperation?"

Pick up the TWO most interesting/appropriate for you:

a) Webinar (live)

b) Training sessions aimed at knowledge transfer from experts):

for instance, a session on the type of energy community projects and legal forms given by representatives of another industrial energy community (transfer of knowledge)

c) Thematic workshops (primarily aimed at sharing good practices and tools on a specific topic):

for instance, a workshop in which we look at examples of energy community projects in Europe and we build a first action plan to expand your energy community

d) Self-paced online learning with videos, guidance materials, exercises, tools, methods...

e) Study visits to organisations to learn more about their practices and share experiences

f) Coaching (receiving individual tailored feedback and advice) "

Closing question: Thank you for all the helpful information you provided. Is there anything you might want to add before we end?

6.2 Questions for stakeholders who are part of an energy community

"Q0. Can you describe your organisation? (scope, activities...)"

"Q1. Can you describe any existing initiatives from your organisation concerning energy sustainability? (what, since when, role in energy community, share of energy coming from renewables installations, are there active plans for the near future...)"

"Q2. What were your organisation's motivations to join the community?"

"Q3. Which benefits do you notice from your organisation's engagement with the energy community?"

"Q4. Which are your main learnings so far from this experience?"

"Q5. To what extent are you aware of the engagement in the community of other organisations in the area and exchange with them on the topic?"

"Q6. Which are the main challenges and problems that your organisation faced when joining and developing your presence in the community?"

"Q7. What kind of support (financial, knowledge, technical...) would help you in expanding your transition to renewables?"

"Q8. (CAPACITY BUILDING) In which of the following areas in relation to the energy transition do you perceive a knowledge/skills need within your organisation?
(SEE TABLE ABOVE)"

"Q9. (CAPACITY BUILDING) Have you attended any capacity-building activity in the past 5 years? Yes/no
If yes: is there a format that you found particularly engaging or effective and that you want to recommend to us?"

"Q10. (CAPACITY BUILDING) What would be the best way for you to conduct training on energy cooperation?

Pick up the TWO most interesting/appropriate for you:

a) Webinar (live)

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for instance, a session on the type of energy community projects and legal forms given by representatives of another industrial energy community (transfer of knowledge)

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for instance, a workshop in which we look at examples of energy community projects in Europe and we build a first action plan to expand your energy community

d) Self-paced online learning with videos, guidance materials, exercises, tools, methods...

e) Study visits to organisations to learn more about their practices and share experiences

f) Coaching (receiving individual tailored feedback and advice) "

Closing question: Thank you for all the helpful information you provided. Is there anything you might want to add before we end?

More information: www.energizcommunity.eu

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